

SMART ERA

Co-design Toolkit/D3.1

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Acronyms

Acronym	Description
CSCW	Computer-Supported Cooperative Work
HCI	Human-Computer Interaction
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
PA	Public Administration
Phygital	Hybrid, phygital and digital, system
SESAM	Smart Era Smartness Assessment Method
SGIs	Services of General Interest
SIP	Smart Innovation Package
Tx.y	Task Tx.y in the SMART ERA workplan
WPx	Work Package x in the SMART ERA workplan

Executive Summary

The SMART ERA project addresses the challenges faced by rural communities in remote areas while defining solutions that foster innovation and socio-economic development. The project proposes a methodology based on collaborative practices that allows the co-design of bundles of enablers that work in synergy to create innovative solutions, called **Smart Innovation Packages**. Enablers, informally called "**ingredients**", may be of different types, as required to face the complexity of introducing innovation in a territory: data and knowledge on context, digital applications, infrastructures, equipment, best practices, communication and training, incentives, financial and economic enablers, political/legal aspects, people.

Work Package 3 of the SMART ERA project aims at formally investigating and defining the conceptual, methodological and operative framework for designing Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs). **This report describes the outcome of the research activities carried out in Task 3.1.**

The report is organised into chapters that progressively explain:

- the rationale behind the adopted definition of SIP,
- a methodology for breaking down a SIP into its "ingredients",
- a set of resources that compose the **SIP Co-design Toolkit** aimed at empowering stakeholders in rural areas to collaboratively design the SIP that best fits their local development challenges,
- an overview of digital functionalities currently under development towards the realisation of a **hybrid (physical and digital) version of the SIP Co-design Toolkit** that will support the motivational strategies elaborated in Task 3.2.

The Annexes of the report offer intuitive examples of SIPs, additional details on the research activities that were carried out within the SMART ERA consortium in Task 3.1 to collect the evidence informing the SIP definition and requirements, insights gathered from a formative evaluation session of the SIP Co-design Toolkit and examples of scenarios illustrating how the toolkit can be used in flexible ways that adapt to different contexts and needs.

1. Introduction

As stated in the project proposal, "the SMART ERA idea stems from the observation that innovative solutions often fail when adopted in isolation. [...] Initiatives are often doomed to be short-lived if not accompanied by solutions for community engagement and policies to incentivize their adoption. SMART ERA will thus address the challenges of rural areas by **integrating a set of solutions** (technological, governance, business, societal, policies, etc.) within **Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs)** in a way to exploit their **synergies** and enhance their effectiveness to achieve a **collective impact which is much higher than the sum of the single components** (Figure 1)".

Figure 1. The SMART ERA concept

The project vision statement thus intuitively defines Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs) as **bundles of technological and non-technological solutions addressing challenges related to rural development**.

Work Package 3 (WP3) of the SMART ERA project aims at formally investigating and defining the conceptual, methodological and operative framework for designing SIPs with and for rural communities. WP3 research is complemented by the multi-dimensional methodology defined in WP2, which is aimed at measuring the smartness and socio-economic dynamics in rural areas to assess the context in which a SIP needs to operate and to evaluate the impact of a SIP's deployment. WP3 also produces co-designed concepts to be implemented in WP4 and tested in the pilot activities of WP5 (Figure 2).

Specific objectives of WP3 are to:

- 1) provide a definition of SIPs starting from the envisioned concept of sets of integrated, digital and non-digital solutions for rural innovation; provide a formal knowledge representation for them; and produce a co-design toolkit that will be used to facilitate SIPs co-design processes (T3.1);

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Figure 2. Work Packages and tasks contributing to the definition, implementation and validation of SIP methodology

- 2) define and implement motivational, gamification-based methods to sustain citizens' participation both during the co-design and co-validation phases (T3.2);
- 3) co-design the SIPs fulfilling the needs of the pilot communities (T3.3);
- 4) develop innovative business models for the sustainability of each SIP (T3.4).

Point 1) above represents the primary goal of task T3.1, which is to generate **an operative definition** of what a Smart Innovation Package (SIP) is and to create **methodological resources** that may support and guide rural areas along the process of co-designing specific SIPs that solve the needs and gaps hampering their development.

This report describes the outcome of the research activities carried out in Task 3.1 and represents Deliverable 3.1.

The report is organised into chapters that progressively explain the rationale behind the provided definition of SIP (Chapter 2), a methodology for decomposing a SIP into its "ingredients" (Chapter 3), and a set of resources that define the "SIP Co-design toolkit" aimed at empowering stakeholders in rural areas to collaboratively create the SIP that best fits their local development challenges (Chapter 4). Chapter 5 provides an overview of digital functionalities currently under development towards the realisation of a hybrid (physical and digital) version of the co-design toolkit that will support the motivational strategies elaborated in T3.2. The Annexes of the report offer intuitive examples of SIPs (Annex A), additional details on the research activities that were carried out within the SMART ERA consortium in T3.1 to collect the evidence informing the SIP definition and requirements (Annexes B, C and D), insights gathered from a formative evaluation session of the toolkit (Annex E) and examples of scenarios illustrating how the SIP Co-design Toolkit can be used in flexible ways that adapt to different contexts and needs (Annex F). Annex G offers additional insights on the design process of the Toolkit.

2. Definition of Smart Innovation Package (SIP)

2.1. Background concepts on collaborative processes

The concept of Smart Innovation Package originates from the recognition that **collaborative processes between Public Administrations, private stakeholders and citizens** which aim at the design of services, their implementation, and their delivery to the community are complex and multifaceted (Leonardi et al., 2023; Not et al., 2024). Innovation is complex because it requires bringing together different knowledge and expertise from various stakeholders, working across organisational and professional boundaries to reach innovative outcomes.

SMART ERA tackles the entire innovation process—from the design to the final delivery and replication of solutions — and aims to **consider innovation as a participatory process in which composite solutions are created**, starting from the assumption that innovative solutions frequently fail when implemented in isolation. Although modern Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) have facilitated the emergence of various technological solutions for rural challenges, these initiatives tend to be short-lived without accompanying community engagement strategies and policies to encourage their adoption. Integrating both social and digital elements is therefore essential for effective rural innovation (Sept, 2020).

One collaborative framework that considers multi-stakeholder governance and the complex factors involved in innovation processes is the "co-production" framework (Brandsen and Honingh, 2015), which stresses the fact that the innovation process does not end with the **collaborative design** of ideas for the service centred around the needs of citizens but extends to the **implementation** and **delivery** phases, where a varied, and dynamic set of stakeholders are engaged. Aspects of continuous **monitoring**, **evaluation** and **sustainability** of the services are also part of the process (Brandsen et al., 2022). Studies further recognize the crucial importance of the preliminary phases of **commissioning** (Nabatchi et al., 2017), and of **political sponsorship** (Leonardi and Not, 2022), **stakeholders' engagement** (Trischler et al., 2019), and **assessment** (Nabatchi et al., 2017). An example of co-production of innovative services is the collaborative development of childcare services where a Public Administration (PA), third-sector education associations, private insurance companies and parents themselves collaborate to design and directly contribute to the delivery of the service (Honingh et al., 2018; Cortesi et al., 2022). Policymakers and governments can play a valuable role by creating and providing an ecosystem that supports the creation of this type of innovation. This requires consolidating **legal, regulatory and policy framework** conditions to foster coordination between actors, ensure the **provision of information** and evidence on needs and demands, create opportunities, facilitate **cross-sectoral coordination**, and provide guidance and support. The need for effective measures to help public-private heterogeneous networks of stakeholders work together is also of utmost importance (Sgaragli, 2014). Community-led territorial development thus requires the creation of an

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ecosystem of **“ingredients”** that go well beyond the practicalities of service delivery (like materials, infrastructures, or human operators).

Furthermore, the distribution of power and responsibility among public and private actors may vary significantly, giving rise to **different governance models** underlying co-production (Linders, 2011).

- “Citizen Sourcing” (or Citizen to Government, C2G) happens when citizens help the government improve public performance and more effectively satisfy the public’s wants and needs.
- “Public-Civic Partnership” (or Government with Citizen, G +C) occurs when the government and citizens share equal power and responsibility.
- “Government as a Platform” (or Government to Citizen, G2C) occurs when the government helps citizens improve their day-to-day productivity, decision-making, and well-being by offering a facilitating platform.
- “Do It Yourself Government” (or Citizen to Citizen, C2C) occurs when citizens help themselves and one another; in this case, the government plays no active role in day-to-day activities but may provide a facilitating framework.

Depending on the territorial context, on the level of citizens’ involvement, on the type of service or innovation, and on who is taking the initiative, **different strategies, “ingredients”, activities, and responsibilities may be needed.**

The goal of SMART ERA is to empower rural communities to co-design, co-develop, and co-validate innovative services to tackle the challenges of rural areas. The SIP-based approach proposed in SMART ERA aims, therefore, to highlight i) the complexity of the innovation process, which does not end with the design or deployment phase but continues with monitoring and replication activities, ii) the necessity of integrating both social and digital elements in the definition of new services, iii) the centrality of multi-stakeholder approaches, in which rural communities play a leading role in the process and, finally, iv) the consideration of the specificities of innovation processes in rural areas, which are different from those occurring in urban contexts.

2.2. The context of SMART ERA rural innovation

SMART ERA integrates both social and digital elements to address the unique challenges and opportunities rural areas present. This approach underscores the importance of fostering **social innovation** by building stronger community ties, promoting inclusive governance, empowering rural populations to participate actively in decision-making processes, and developing solutions tailored to their needs and specificities. SMART ERA also emphasises the **role of digital technologies and data** in transforming rural practices, enhancing connectivity, and improving access to resources and services. By **combining social and digital dimensions**, SMART ERA rural innovation aims to create sustainable, resilient rural environments that can adapt to emerging global trends such as climate change, economic shifts, and evolving societal needs. The following paragraphs briefly summarise some relevant aspects of these two dimensions.

2.2.1. Social aspects

According to the European Commission (2013), **social innovation** involves "developing and implementing new ideas—whether products, services, or models—to **address social needs and foster new social relationships or collaborations**". It encompasses actions, participatory processes, and outcomes that drive changes in social relations, collective empowerment, political structures, governance, and overall improvements in the social system. As stated by Moulaert et al. (2013), social innovation initiatives must not only address immediate social needs but also facilitate broader transformations in community dynamics and governance. Successful rural social innovations are characterised by their ability to empower local populations, fostering collaboration among diverse stakeholders and enhancing community resilience. By solving fundamental problems and encouraging social change, these initiatives create a conducive environment for cooperation and collective action, ultimately leading to **sustainable improvements in the social fabric of rural areas**. This approach underlines the importance of integrating social relations and governance processes into the design and implementation of innovative solutions tailored to the unique challenges faced by rural communities (Moulaert et al., 2013).

According to Neumeier (2017), for social innovation to be considered successful, it should introduce something new to users, context, or application, address needs more effectively than existing solutions, provide lasting outcomes, and be adopted beyond its initial development group. The main phases of social innovation are: 1) *problematization*, when a small group identifies a need (prompted by external or internal factors like threats or interests) and forms a team to address it; 2) *expression of interest*, when additional participants and stakeholders join as they see benefits in involvement; 3) *delineation and coordination*, when participants collaborate, sharing skills and knowledge, and co-develop a new form of organised action. When this collaborative approach gains widespread acceptance and proves better than traditional methods, it qualifies as a social innovation.

The literature on social innovation has often overlooked the specific dynamics of **rural social innovation**. Definitions of rural social innovation have emerged to clarify its essence and guide further development. Moulaert et al. (2013) emphasise that for an initiative to qualify as a rural social innovation, it must address the satisfaction of community needs, instigate changes in socio-political structures, and empower local populations. Successful rural social innovations are characterised by their ability to **enhance welfare and resilience within communities**, effectively tackling fundamental issues while fostering social change and collaboration among various stakeholders (Kusumastuti et al., 2023).

According to Kusumastuti (2023), understanding the **unique challenges of rural areas**, such as economic conditions, access to public services, migration patterns, and gender imbalances, is crucial for promoting practical social innovation. Rural innovation typically relies on two key groups: those with local knowledge and experience, who can engage communities, and those with technical skills, who can develop sustainable technologies to boost productivity.

The governance issue is crucial in studies on rural innovation. Two major challenges arise when the central government seeks to encourage rural social innovation. First, as Neumeier (2017) notes, social innovation in rural development cannot be easily initiated or directed from a top-down approach. This limitation often results in initiatives that do not resonate with local needs or priorities. Second, limited funding and support frequently leads to incomplete,

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unsustainable, or failed efforts. Rural administrations are often compelled to implement innovations mandated by the central government that may not align with local resources or community interests. As a result, even when rural governments succeed in implementing innovations, the results often don't meet expectations and are not sustainable. This highlights the need for a governance approach focusing on local involvement and flexibility, ensuring that innovations are practical and effective in addressing rural communities' specific challenges.

Mertens (2022) highlights the unique aspects of social innovation in rural areas, emphasising the role of new actors beyond traditional R&D departments, start-ups, or universities typical of city contexts. **Rural innovation often relies on local people and groups working together.** This collective action becomes essential because rural areas may lack access to traditional markets and resources. Social innovation in these settings aims to improve life in local communities, making it both a community-driven effort and a shared responsibility among residents.

According to OECD reports (2014), rural innovation relies on voluntary efforts, creativity, and local contributions, often involving various stakeholders and knowledge sources. Public investment is crucial for scaling successful rural innovations and establishing supportive institutions. While innovation enhances productivity and competitiveness in rural areas, identifying innovative actions within these communities can be challenging.

Four key points emerge that SMART ERA should consider:

- Rural communities should have the authority to recognize their strengths, aspire ambitiously, and lead local innovation initiatives.
- Policymakers should empower rural communities to engage actively in innovation efforts.
- Policies designed for urban settings frequently neglect the specific needs of rural areas, underscoring the necessity for tailored rural governance.
- New governance models and metrics are essential, as traditional indicators like patents and R&D expenditures often overlook rural innovation activities.

In summary, several social aspects should be considered to ensure **relevance, acceptance and sustainability** of social innovation in rural areas, such as the crucial role played by the local community, the importance of the governance models, and the consideration of economic aspects.

2.2.2. Digital aspects

The digital aspects are increasingly recognized as crucial for enhancing the competitiveness and sustainability of rural economies (European Parliament, 2021). Digitalization relies on technological innovation, and numerous advancements contribute to this broader phenomenon.

Early studies on ICT and rural innovation focused on the adoption of ICTs and how to adapt them to rural contexts (Salemink et al., 2017). Much work has been conducted on teleworking and telemedicine in rural European regions, highlighting the transformative

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potential of digital solutions in **enhancing access to services and improving quality of life** (Martinez et al., 2004; López-Igual et al., 2020).

Yin and colleagues (2022) examine the importance of rural innovation systems in promoting sustainable development in rural areas. Digital transformation is emphasised as a tool for boosting productivity and connectivity, offering **new business opportunities** through improved access to ICT. At the same time, the authors stress the need for active stakeholder engagement, which ensures that local actors collaborate to identify and address critical challenges. Effective policies are necessary to support rural innovation systems. Besides, the importance of aligning national and local policies to create an enabling environment for innovation is stressed, as well as the importance of sustainability in rural development, advocating for practices that **promote ecological balance** while fostering economic growth.

Recently, researchers in Computer-Supported Cooperative Work (CSCW) and Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) started to focus on "developing regions", leading to an increasing interest in understanding how ICTs can support quality of life and work practices, such as agriculture in developing countries (Chandra and Collis, 2021). These scholars acknowledge the challenges faced by rural communities, including limited access to electricity and water, while also highlighting the innovative ICT solutions that arise in response, such as solar-powered mobile phone charging systems. If studies have focused at the beginning mainly on rural challenges faced in developing countries, studies are recently addressing the challenges specific to developed rural areas.

Hardy et al. (2019), in their work “*Rural HCI Research: Definitions, Distinctions, Methods, and Opportunities*”, propose a research agenda focused on rural areas that differ from the low-income, developing regions typically studied in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI). The authors emphasise the need to explore rural areas in developed and high-income countries, which remain largely understudied in HCI research despite having access to technology and infrastructure.

In their scoping review, the authors first identify key characteristics of rural areas, including infrastructure such as internet connectivity and the scarcity of public services like transportation, often due to low population density and geographic isolation. Rural areas tend to be far from urban centres, and their culture and values are closely linked to this isolation. The peculiar relationship with nature shapes local economies and businesses in rural regions, which are typically smaller and often focused on agriculture and resource extraction. Digital literacy and computer skills can vary significantly, as can access to social services and health care. Rural populations are generally smaller and less dense, with demographics often skewing older. Social networks in rural areas also differ from those in urban environments, with more family-based relationships compared to the friend-centred networks commonly found in cities. As a result, network-mediated aid in rural areas is more likely to come from family connections rather than friends.

In their scoping review, Hardy et al. (2019) also identify a number of trends and the role of ICT in rural areas. They found that most of the research has been conducted in developing or low-income countries, with studies in high-income regions mainly focusing on the US, UK, and Australia. Many papers did not explicitly define "rurality", though when definitions were present, they were often descriptive rather than sociocultural or symbolic definitions. A significant emphasis has been placed on **infrastructure challenges**, especially limited internet connectivity, which is a primary factor influencing technology access and adoption in rural areas. Consequently, many studies explore technologies that aim to bridge the rural-

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urban divide, often highlighting **digital literacy** and the need to **align technology with rural values** in the design process. Research concerning rural economies and services tends to focus on agriculture and healthcare support, while studies on social dynamics suggest that population size and density affect online social network engagement and user-generated content production. Qualitative and cross-sectional methodologies are predominant, with observational methods slightly more common, reflecting a focus on understanding user experiences in rural contexts.

2.2.3. The SIP-based approach to rural innovation

By combining social and digital dimensions of innovation, the SMART ERA project takes on rural development challenges by:

- devising methods and tools to help rural communities **assess their context** and identify priorities;
- devising methods and tools aimed at **supporting the participatory design of packages of "ingredients"** (social, technological, political, financial, related to impact and sustainability), called Smart Innovation Packages, for implementing innovative solutions to rural development challenges;
- implementing **motivational strategies** to sustain community engagement and the achievement of innovation goals;
- with the help of 6 diverse pilot case studies, **experimenting with the usage of these methods and tools**, as well as observing actual co-creation processes that help refine the methodology and let best practices emerge;
- experimenting with the **implementation of some "ingredients"** for SIPs to test the overall approach;
- distilling **lessons learned** and policy briefs;
- defining **replication procedures** that trigger virtuous cycles for scaling up and spreading innovation.

Figure 3 summarises the SMART ERA vision of the SIP-based approach to innovation, with the enablers provided by the outputs produced in the project.

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Figure 3. The path from a rural challenge to a validated innovation solution. In orange the added value to the process provided by the SMART ERA project

2.3. Process followed for SIP definition and SIP co-design toolkit creation

Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs) are the pivotal concept that permeates the overall SMART ERA workplan. This means that the definition of SIP and the co-design toolkit produced at the end of the first year of project development represent **living concepts and materials** that will be tested, refined, and reflected upon during the whole project development in an incremental process, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The incremental process of SIPs framework definition, piloting, evaluation and replication in the SMART ERA workplan

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This deliverable focuses on activities carried out within T3.1 during the first year of project implementation and that enabled the distilling of requirements, the operative definition of **Smart Innovation Package**, the draft of a formal description template, the identification of main categories of SIP "ingredients", and the creation of a methodological toolkit with resources supporting the co-design of SIPs tackling specific rural innovation challenges.

Figure 5 summarises the flow of activities performed in T3.1 and their interdependencies (Highlighted in orange are workshops held with the participation of all project partners. White boxes correspond to research activities conducted by technical partners contributing to T3.1).

Figure 5. The flow of activities performed in Task 3.1

Starting from background research on collaborative processes involving public-private networks of stakeholders for the co-production of innovative services and on the peculiarities of the rural context, a participatory journey was initiated that involved SMART ERA Community Activators and Pilot Orchestrators for the six project case studies in refining the meaning and concepts of SIPs beginning from concrete examples and practices of rural development.

1. **Reflection on previous participatory processes for co-creating innovation services in rural areas.** Activities started with an initial in-presence workshop during which Community Activators were asked to share and reflect, with the help of Pilot Orchestrators, on previous experiences organised in their rural territory for the collaborative creation of innovation, on the type of service that was created, on the creation process that was followed, and on the positive vs. challenging aspects that were encountered. The innovation stories and the comments that emerged during the workshop discussion were analysed to identify commonalities and differences

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across diverse experiences and rural contexts. Best practices, barriers and sustainability issues were identified for each sample process, trying to understand which strategies and innovative "ingredients" were used to solve challenges during the initiation phase, the stakeholder network engagement, the context analysis, the project implementation, its sustained maintenance and monitoring in time.

For the sake of research replicability, Annex B describes in detail how the workshop was organised, which materials were produced and the findings that were derived. This activity's results have fed the requirements that SIPs should satisfy to support innovation processes in rural areas, as described in Section 2.4.

2. **Reflection on types of "ingredients" required to deploy innovation services.**

The output of the first workshop provided the background for a second workshop, during which all consortium members were asked to identify different types of "ingredients" that come into play during the participatory creation and deployment of innovation services in rural areas. The workshop was held in presence in the form of a brainstorming session within four parallel work groups of about 9 - 14 participants each, as well as a final plenary discussion session. The analysis of the material collected during the workshop allowed the creation of an affinity diagram where 157 sample ingredients were grouped into ten main categories of factors that may be present in a SIP (data and knowledge on context, software, best practices, communication and training, incentives, financial and economic enablers, infrastructure, equipment, political/legal aspects, people).

Annex C describes in detail the workshop whose results validated the SMART ERA overall vision that solutions to rural development challenges require complementary types of actions that work in synergy. Preliminary ideas on how to structure a categorization of ingredients to support the creation of SIPs were derived from the output of this workshop.

A literature study was then initiated to deepen the understanding of the categories of SIP ingredients and integrate what has emerged so far with existing research findings and experiences from other EU projects. This desk research work helped consolidate the structure of the categorization of "ingredients" illustrated in Chapter 3.

3. **Reflection on digital "ingredients" and SIP co-design methods.**

The literature study helped prepare a third workshop with Community Activators and Pilot Orchestrators to brainstorm on the opportunities that software/digital ingredients may open for rural areas. On the one hand, this activity allowed pilot owners to start reflecting on how digital technologies may become special ingredients for SIPs, what sample technology seems most promising for their pilot and which scenario can be envisaged, what stakeholders should be involved in implementing the scenario, what would assure that the solution would work, and/or which would be the expected benefits. On the other hand, the workshop also worked as a test experiment to refine co-design methodologies that have been included in the SIP Co-design Toolkit (like thematic cards to illustrate a variety of sample ingredients of a specific category and reflection canvases), as will be described in Chapter 4.

Annex D describes in detail how the workshop was organised and the materials used to facilitate the discussion.

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4. **Operative definition of SIP and SIP Co-design Toolkit specification.** The results of the collaborative activities and research performed at previous stages were used to elaborate a preliminary operative definition of what a SIP is (Section 2.5) and to conceive resources and guidelines (the SIP Co-design Toolkit described in Chapter 4) to help networks of stakeholders in the co-design of a SIP that fits the needs of their local territory.
Joint discussions have also been initiated with T3.2 on how motivational strategies could be incorporated into the co-design toolkit to support the engagement of stakeholders throughout the SIP creation process.
5. **Formative evaluation of the SIP Co-Design Toolkit and training.** Preliminary feedback by project partners on the structure and contents of the SIP Co-design Toolkit was collected during a workshop organised in conjunction with the consortium meeting held in Milano on the 3rd and 4th of December 2024. The workshop served the purpose of validating the interaction with analogue materials (formative evaluation) as well as the purpose of offering hands-on training on its use. Annex E describes in detail how the training and validation workshop was organised and the main reflections that will be used to refine the toolkit.

2.4. SIP requirements

The research activities performed in the initial phases of the SMART ERA project, starting from the analysis of the workshops described above, led to the emergence of specific requirements for the conceptual definition of SIPs. In particular, the following findings emerging from Workshop 1 (described in detail in Annex B) and Workshop 2 (described in detail in Annex C) are of particular significance.

- Local rural areas first need help to **build capacity** in implementing innovation.
- The variety of governance models at the basis of rural innovation co-production calls for a **flexible concept of SIP in terms of ideation, management and ownership**.
- It may take **a long time** to reach the end of the service creation process. For this reason, an **incremental approach** to service creation is often adopted.
- **Replicating** the process, with lessons learned, in a new municipality or for a new product is also an applied strategy.
- Achieving **early success stories** helps the incremental approach, favours replicability, helps find funding and helps return results to stakeholders.
- The solution to a rural challenge may be a bundle of services (e.g., health education, proximity services, telemedicine services); therefore, **complementarity** between actions may be required.
- The implementation of the service might need to ensure its **adaptability** over time to adapt to changing seasons, regional needs, or different users' needs.

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- Continuity of action sometimes comes from the **complementarity of different funding opportunities**.
- It is important to **monitor the progress** of the process and implement **periodic evaluation** and improvements to take into account the feedback from stakeholders.
- Concrete examples of ingredients proposed by experts or coming from the **experience of other territories, are of inspiration** for rural communities committed to innovation.
- **Motivation** of participants is essential. There must be effective ways to activate it and sustain it in time. Indeed, different stakeholders may participate at different stages of the process.

These findings have been translated into the following operative requirements for SIPs:

1. **INTUITIVENESS.** An intuitive methodology and framework to develop SIPs is required to help heterogeneous networks of stakeholders build capacity and share a common understanding of solutions.
2. **COLLABORATION.** SIP's conceptualisation should support its collaborative creation and flexible management.
3. **USERS DIVERSITY.** Different types of stakeholders may orchestrate a SIP co-production process. Therefore, flexibility has to be guaranteed in terms of how a SIP is used and by whom.
4. **INCREMENTALITY.** The operative definition of a SIP has to accommodate the progressive identification and implementation of ingredients easily.
5. **SUBPARTS.** Subsets of ingredients in SIPs may constitute meaningful clusters that solve subproblems related to the overall innovation challenge. Clusters could be focussed on individually and could be reused separately.
6. **COMMUNICABILITY.** Intermediate results of the SIP co-design that represent successful stories need to be communicable in an intuitive way.
7. **REPLICABILITY.** A SIP or its subparts need to provide a sort of "recipe" to help their replication, e.g., by the same territory to scale up the approach to a more extensive area or to a different type of service, or by a distinct territory with similar needs.
8. **ADAPTABILITY.** Replication in a different context or the usage of a SIP at a different time may require adapting the set of ingredients.
9. **COMPLEMENTARITY.** SIPs generated from different projects may need to be complementary, e.g. to share some ingredients or to become subparts of a larger SIP.

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10. **OVERVIEW.** SIPs should have a representation that allows identifying at a glance the state of progress, the type of ingredients that have been identified so far and whether there are categories that have not been considered yet.
11. **DESCRIPTION and SEARCHABILITY.** SIPs should be described in simple terms to help other territories immediately grasp what was done and its impact to get inspiration. Further details on the SIP ingredients should be made available to facilitate followers' actual take-up.
12. **MOTIVATION.** The process for SIPs co-design should be supported with motivational strategies to stimulate and sustain participation.

2.5. Operative definition of Smart Innovation Package

The research activities performed during the SMART ERA initial phase and presented in the previous sections provide the background to the following conceptual framework for Smart Innovation Packages.

Definition

A **Smart Innovation Package (SIP)** is a set of integrated enablers that work in synergy to provide a solution to a rural innovation challenge. Enablers, informally called "**ingredients**", may be of different types, as required to face the complexity of introducing innovation in a territory: various types of actors and incentives to motivate them, data and knowledge on the context, digital applications, infrastructures, equipment, financial and economic enablers, political advocacy, legal aspects, communication and training activities may be all required to set up a solution that works and is socially, environmentally and economically sustainable.

Complementary ingredients may be necessary to:

- establish the collaborative processes that prepare the ground for the service/innovation,
- implement the service itself,
- maintain it in the long term.

Visual representation metaphor

A visual metaphor was selected to intuitively convey the concept of complementary ingredients created collaboratively in a joint effort (**INTUITIVENESS** requirement).

The **hexagon shape** to represent ingredients was preferred over that of a puzzle piece (used in the project proposal to introduce the SIP concept) to better support the idea that aggregations of hexagons are easier to compose, to incrementally create flexible shapes that may adapt to different spaces (contexts). At the same time, the evocative **structure of beehives** suggests the possibility of providing clear guidance on how to collaboratively work at filling gaps.

This visual representation metaphor was adopted very soon at the beginning of the project to test its intuitiveness within the heterogeneous group of project partners, who have very

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different backgrounds. Figure 6 shows one of the very first examples of a visual representation of SIP shared with partners (at the consortium meeting in Mallorca in June 2024).

Figure 6. Visual representation of a sample SIP

This example was used to intuitively explain how a rural challenge of limited agricultural development due to a lack of modern equipment could be solved by creating a cooperative of local farmers to facilitate the renting of expensive equipment. The example was inspired by a real challenge faced by a rural community in Marene (Italy). To build the final solution (SIP), stakeholders first needed to better understand the context of the problem (mustard-coloured ingredient hexagons), set up the legal, financial and regulatory structure of the cooperative (turquoise ingredient hexagons), create networking and communication strategies (white ingredient hexagons). The pale blue hexagons exemplify how this existing case study could be further innovated by using digital technologies to optimise the management of the equipment.

This visual representation also supports the requirement of providing, at a glance, the state of progress and the ingredients identified so far (**OVERVIEW** requirement). It allows to visually highlight subparts that solve specific problems and can be communicated as intermediate success stories (**SUBPARTS** and **COMMUNICABILITY** requirements). It easily permits the incremental growth of the SIP or the change of some ingredients (**INCREMENTALITY**, **ADAPTABILITY**). It allows to put side-by-side SIPs created for different challenges to identify common ingredients and overlapping items (**COMPLEMENTARITY**).

Formal representation

In addition to its very intuitive visual representation, a SIP needs to be described in good detail to document what was done, help other territories get inspiration and facilitate the replication, with adaptation, of the solution. A common template to structure and annotate

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SIP descriptions was defined for this purpose, as illustrated in Section 4.2. (requirements of **DESCRIPTION, SEARCHABILITY, REPLICABILITY**).

How different types of stakeholders may collaborate in the co-design of a SIP is favoured by a bespoke SIP Co-design Toolkit, as described in Chapter 4 and in the usage scenarios exemplified in Annex F (**COLLABORATION** and **USERS DIVERSITY** requirements). How to support the motivation of stakeholders along the whole SIP co-design and co-delivery process is currently being investigated in Task 3.2 and will be described in detail in deliverable 3.2 at month 24 of project development (**MOTIVATION** requirement). An explanation of how motivational strategies will be supported by digital functionalities complementing analogue materials of the SIP Co-design Toolkit is offered in Chapter 5.

3. Categorization of SIP "ingredients"

The findings that emerged from the activities carried out within T3.1 in collaboration with the project partners (detailed in Annex C) led to the identification of different types of ingredients that work in synergy to implement rural innovation. Through the analysis of existing literature and experiences from other EU projects, this initial categorisation was refined, integrated and consolidated to include the 12 categories and related subcategories shown in Figure 8.

It is important to note that SMART ERA does not aim to create an exhaustive catalogue of ingredients for rural innovation, as this would be an encyclopaedic task whose effort goes beyond the project's scope. Furthermore, ingredients can potentially be categorised in alternative ways. For example, strategies for community engagement can be considered as potentially belonging to a separate category of "Best practices", or they can be regarded as essential ingredients to frame the "People" category better.

The categorisation proposed here has the main objective of **offering rural communities stimuli for reflecting on what may be needed to assemble an effective SIP**. However, it does not aim at being all-encompassing.

The categorization will be kept **flexible and open** to further refinements and integration during the project, also benefiting from the feedback and contribution from the actual SIP creation activities by the six pilot use cases and follower regions.

As will be described further in Chapter 4, the categorization of ingredients serves as the foundation for developing the "Ingredient Cards" and other resources that form the core of the SIP Co-design Toolkit (Figure 7).

Figure 7. An example of resources developed for the category "Digital applications": cards, reflection questions and "How to"

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Figure 8. List of ingredient categories and subcategories included in the first version of the SIP Co-design Toolkit

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As a convention, a colour code has been associated with each ingredient category. This may allow to quickly recognize ingredients of the same type in a SIP visual representation.

In the following sections of this chapter we provide a general definition for each of the 12 identified ingredient categories, together with 68 examples of more specific subcategories. These examples have emerged from collaborative activities with Community Activators and Pilot Orchestrators (e.g., the workshops described in Annex B and Annex C) and from relevant bibliography on rural innovation.

Given the wide range of possible development challenges faced by rural areas, the selection of the examples was purposefully focused on ingredient types potentially more relevant for the SMART ERA pilot case studies.

3.1. People

Involving different categories of people ensures that innovations in rural areas are relevant, accepted, and sustainable. The knowledge and expertise that local actors bring to the table allow for a deep understanding of the specific challenges, needs, and opportunities within their communities (Jungsberg et al., 2020). This insight ensures that innovations are not only tailored to the unique context of rural areas but also resonate with the people who will be using them, leading to a greater acceptance and long-term success. By engaging stakeholders, solutions are grounded in local realities and are better equipped to drive meaningful and lasting change in rural communities (Vercher, 2022).

A wide range of actors might be involved depending on the sector and the problem to be addressed, as exemplified below.

Governmental and administrative public bodies

Government agencies at various levels (local, regional, and national) provide the necessary political and economic support for rural innovation. They create policies, funding opportunities, and regulatory frameworks that facilitate innovation processes.

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Their engagement can be top-down or bottom-up (Gao, 2016). In a top-down approach, public agencies at higher levels of government (national or regional) set the agenda for innovation. They develop policies, allocate funding, and implement programs to stimulate innovation in rural areas. This approach often involves large-scale initiatives like infrastructure development, technological upgrades, or agricultural modernisation. The top-down method can ensure significant resources and direction but may lack sensitivity to local needs and conditions if not adequately informed by grassroots input.

In contrast, a bottom-up approach emphasises local involvement and grassroots initiatives. In this case, public agencies at the local level work closely with rural communities to identify needs, develop solutions, and support innovations that emerge from the ground up. This approach is more responsive to the specific challenges and opportunities within a community, ensuring that innovations are relevant and widely accepted. The bottom-up method fosters local ownership and engagement, making it more sustainable in the long term. Ideally, public agencies should integrate both methods, using top-down support to amplify locally driven innovations (Gao, 2016).

Examples of actors at the local level are city or municipal planning departments and local housing authorities. At a regional level, we can have, for example, regional development agencies or regional environmental protection agencies. At a national level, are the Ministry of Agriculture, national health departments or ministries, and digital transition departments.

Local Communities

Local community members possess valuable knowledge about their environment, needs, and challenges. Their involvement ensures that innovations are relevant and tailored to local contexts. Community members often participate in co-design processes, helping to generate, coordinate, and promote effective innovations (Chirenje et al., 2013).

Examples of local community actors are residents, community leaders and “local heroes”, farmers and agricultural producers, youth and students, indigenous and cultural groups, “back to nature” people and “neo-rurals”, nomad workers.

Visitors and tourists

Despite not living there year-round, people with a strong personal and emotional connection to the territory, such as second homeowners, people who visit frequently for holidays or seasonal stays, and relatives of permanent residents, can play a valuable role in community development. While they are not part of the community's daily life, they can contribute by participating in local events, supporting local businesses, and engaging in social or cultural activities. Because of their ties, they can influence local development and community dynamics, bringing external perspectives and potentially advocating for the area's needs and interests.

Also, occasional tourists bring to the table specific requirements, points of view and opportunities for participation.

Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and local associations

NGOs and civil society organisations often act as intermediaries. They can mobilise resources, provide expertise, and facilitate collaboration among stakeholders. These organisations frequently focus on social issues and advocate for marginalised groups, ensuring that rural innovations are inclusive and equitable.

Examples of local associations are women's groups and youth associations.

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Academic and research Institutions

Academic institutions contribute to rural innovation by conducting research, providing technical expertise, and developing new technologies. Examples of actors from academia and research are universities and research centres focused on technological development, universities of Social Sciences, and secondary institutes addressing topics related to rural development, such as hospitality schools.

Private sector actors and entrepreneurs

The private sector, including local businesses and entrepreneurs, is critical for driving innovation through investment, technology development, and market access. Their involvement can lead to the creation of new products, services, and business models that enhance economic opportunities in rural areas.

Actors in this subcategory include digital transition experts, IT solution architects, business model experts, start-ups, and telecom companies.

Innovation brokers and facilitators

Innovation brokers are individuals or organisations that facilitate connections and collaborations among various stakeholders. They help build networks, engage and mobilise community members, develop shared language, and articulate innovation needs.

Experts and professionals

This subcategory includes other actors with specific skills that can help the rural innovation process, like experts in digital literacy, technology, service design, and education, as well as training professionals, funding advisors, government and policy advisors, and digital transition officers.

3.2. Data

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Data provide insights that can enhance problem understanding and territorial assessment, support decision-making, resource allocation, community engagement, service design, and enable the actual execution and monitoring of innovative services.

- In the first phases of a project, data can be gathered from various sources to **identify local needs, challenges, and opportunities**. Socio-demographic and economic data can be used to understand trends and needs regarding social and economic development.
- Data can then be **at the core of digital services** meant to support rural innovation (as further discussed for the "Digital applications" ingredient category in Section 3.4.)
- In the deployment phase, data are generated when **monitoring** the execution of innovations. Similarly, in the **evaluation** phase, the impact on community well-being or economic growth requires data analysis.

Data may be inherently **digital** or may be represented by **knowledge, ideas and opinions** which are not originally coming in digital form (e.g. information to be extracted from documents, verbal communications, expert consultation, civic consultation).

Digital data, in particular, is gaining an increasingly important role in rural innovation (Salemink et al., 2017). For instance, data from telephony operators and mobility patterns can provide insights into population flows and density, which can inform infrastructure development and service provision. Environmental sensors offer real-time air, soil, and water quality data, enabling evidence-based agriculture and improved environmental management. In livestock farming, biometric sensors and IoT infrastructure monitor animal health and behaviour, supporting big data analytics to identify trends and ensure animal welfare. Drones and satellite images contribute to the early detection of fires and the monitoring of land status while also allowing for large-scale livestock monitoring (Alanezi et al., 2022). Data related to farm products, when combined with blockchain technology, guarantee the traceability of animal products from farm to table, enhancing product quality and safety. Crowdsourced data and digital twins further enrich the data ecosystem, providing predictive insights and fostering a collaborative approach to rural development.

Data can be categorised in different ways according to their format, timeframe and sensitivity (Table 1). A common precondition to all types of data is that their quality is suited for the desired goal, ensuring for example accessibility, accuracy, completeness, consistency, timeliness, validity, uniqueness, relevance, and compliance to data protection regulations.

Table 1. Different types of data

Category	Type	Description
By format	Quantitative Data	Numerical data that can be measured and analysed statistically, such as sales numbers, temperature readings, and population counts.

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	Qualitative Data	Descriptive, non-numerical data, such as interview transcripts, observations, and social media comments, often used to capture meanings, concepts, or perceptions.
By timeframe	Real-Time Data	Captured and processed instantly as data are generated, often used in monitoring systems, financial trading, and IoT applications.
	Historical Data	Collected over time and used to analyse past trends, predict future outcomes, or understand patterns, such as weather or historical sales data.
By sensitivity	Public Data	Data that is openly available to the public and does not contain sensitive or confidential information, like public records and open data sets.
	Confidential Data	Information restricted to authorised personnel, such as personal identifiers, financial details, or proprietary business data.
	Sensitive Data	Data requiring special handling to protect privacy and security; they are often governed by regulations, such as health records, financial information, and personal data protected under GDPR.

The Data ingredient category can be further divided into several subcategories. Here is a non-exhaustive list.

Demographic and socio-economic data

Data on population density, age distribution, income levels, employment rates, development of different economic sectors, availability of services, and digitalisation levels constitute the basis for understanding the needs and challenges of rural communities and social transformations in time. This information can guide the initial assessment of potential areas of intervention, policy-making and resource distribution to ensure that actions are targeted effectively. Socio-economic data can also aid ex-post evaluation of interventions or historical trends. For example, the European Commission's rural observatory¹ provides data on healthcare access, education, and economic conditions, which can be used to inform local development strategies.

Infrastructure and connectivity data

Information on broadband availability and quality is strategic, as connectivity is a prerequisite for implementing digital technologies. Projects to improve internet access in rural areas highlight the importance of mapping connectivity gaps to ensure digital services reach those who most need them. Reliable connectivity is a cornerstone for economic growth and improved quality of life in rural areas. High-speed internet empowers local businesses to participate in e-commerce, access larger markets, and adopt modern technologies, driving economic dynamism.

¹ <https://observatory.rural-vision.europa.eu/?lng=en&ctx=RUROBS> (last accessed on the 18th of November 2024).

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Livestock farming data

Monitoring sensors, IoT infrastructures, and other methods can support the collection of data related to livestock farming. These data can help improve production efficiency, for example, by identifying optimal feeding regimens, monitoring environmental impact towards more sustainable practices, and enhancing animal health management.

Wildlife data

Wildlife data refers to collecting and analysing information regarding wild animal populations, their behaviours, and habitats to improve wildlife management, conservation efforts, and ecological research. Wildlife data encompasses a diverse range of information (Neethirajan and Kemp, 2021). For instance, species observations involve records of wildlife sightings gathered through methods like field surveys, camera traps, and citizen reporting. These observations are fundamental for mapping species distribution and tracking population trends. Besides, habitat information focuses on the ecosystems where species thrive, such as forests, wetlands, or grasslands, and examines the environmental conditions sustaining these populations.

Environmental and geographical data

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and environmental data can assist in land use planning, resource management, and disaster preparedness. This data type helps make informed decisions that consider environmental sustainability alongside economic development.

Health and well-being data

The digital collection of personal health data enables telemedicine services in remote areas. At a more strategic level, monitoring health indicators and quality of life metrics can help identify areas needing intervention, such as healthcare access and social services that improve the overall well-being of rural residents. Collecting health and well-being data can significantly support rural innovation by providing insights that enhance healthcare delivery, improve community resilience, and foster economic development.

Industry-specific data

Each economic sector or industry relies on data that can help businesses and organizations make informed decisions, optimize operations, and improve overall performance. The type of data useful in a specific economic sector can vary widely depending on the nature of the sector. For instance, the tourism industry counts on visitor numbers and demographics, accommodation occupancy rates, seasonal trends and patterns, customer satisfaction and feedback, economic impact assessments, data on mobility. It therefore requires an integration of data coming from heterogeneous sources, with the collaboration of hotels, owners of private accommodation solutions, restaurants, public transport companies, rent-a-car companies, other providers of tourist services, etc.

The agriculture sector needs instead to collect data from cooperatives, farmers, local producers, and other actors of the supply chain. Weather patterns and forecasts, market prices for crops, pest and disease incidence are other types of data that might be needed.

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Citizen science and community data

This cross-cutting category of data may relate to different domains (e.g. agriculture, land use and status, livestock, wild flora and fauna, ...) and is referred to engaging local populations in data collection through citizen science initiatives. It is worth being distinguished as this approach not only gathers valuable information but also fosters community involvement and ownership of development projects. Citizen science and community science can indeed be considered forms of crowdsourced data. These approaches involve the participation of the general public in the collection, analysis, and dissemination of data related to scientific research, environmental monitoring, and community issues. A wide array of data can be collected collaboratively, including agricultural land use, soil quality, weather conditions, phenology, crop calendars, and the presence of weeds, pests, and diseases.

3.3. Local knowledge

According to OECD reports (2014), rural innovation relies on voluntary efforts, creativity, and local contributions, often involving various stakeholders and knowledge sources. In addition to data that can be formally represented and often digitally collected, a relevant type of information that is needed to develop innovative solutions for rural areas is represented by "local knowledge". This term carries different meanings across various domains. It refers to beliefs and orientations rooted in a community's historical social practices, with their own rationale and validity distinct from global knowledge forms. It contrasts with institutional knowledge and it denotes knowledge that diverges from established paradigms, circulating unofficially among smaller groups (Canagarajah, 2002). It also describes the context-specific strategies practitioners develop in their work and the practical know-how of rural inhabitants and producers (Csurgó et al. 2008). Recognizing and valuing local knowledge empowers rural areas inhabitants to take an active role in innovation efforts. When local voices are included in decision-making processes, this fosters a sense of ownership over initiatives and encourages greater engagement (Kusumastuti et al. 2023).

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Community perspectives and values

Values, viewpoints and beliefs shared by members of a community shape how individuals understand their environment and provide valuable insights on how a community might creatively respond to local challenges, fostering engagement with innovative solutions. In the context of rural innovation, **community values** help shape initiatives that are relevant, sustainable, and accepted by local residents. For instance, as suggested by Hardy et al. (2019) the relationship with Nature of inhabitants of rural areas can be different from that of urban people. Values related to Nature are shaped by productive practices, local traditions and specific forms of natural resources extraction and it is important to understand them when introducing innovative practices and solutions. Taking into account **attitudes and beliefs** held by members of a community helps ensure acceptability of solutions and sustainability of initiatives. **Creative ideas** by community members should be highly valued, as they are tailored to address local challenges with originality.

Traditional and cultural knowledge

Traditional or "indigenous" knowledge is knowledge rooted in the experiences gained through long-term interactions with the environment and is often adapted to local cultural contexts. Traditional knowledge encompasses a wide range of information, including agricultural practices, medicinal uses of plants and ecological management techniques. This knowledge is typically transmitted orally from one generation to the next, traditional knowledge is considered collectively owned by the community rather than by individuals. It is useful in various fields, particularly in agriculture, fisheries, health care, and environmental management.

Local expertise

Community members possess valuable insights about their environment, agricultural practices, and socio-economic conditions. This localised knowledge can inform innovative practices that enhance productivity, sustainability, and resilience in rural areas. For example, local entrepreneurs often have insights into market dynamics, consumer preferences, and effective business practices. Likewise, farmers may have expertise about specific breeds of cattle that are well-suited to the local climate and terrain.

3.4. Digital applications

Digital technologies are increasingly important for driving sustainable rural development, offering significant benefits across various sectors (European Parliament, 2021; OECD Report, 2007). However, this requires coordinated efforts to build infrastructures, skills, and innovation ecosystems. A holistic approach integrating digital tools with traditional strengths is required (ENRD Report, 2015).

Precision farming, IoT sensors, and data analytics enhance **agricultural productivity and livestock management** by providing real-time data, optimising inputs, and increasing yields. Digital platforms **improve market access** for rural producers, empowering them economically. Additionally, digital tools enable **new business models**, such as rural tourism and remote services, fostering economic diversification and job creation. Investments in rural broadband and digital services like **telemedicine and distance learning** improve connectivity and access to opportunities, bridging the urban-rural divide. Moreover, digital technologies support **sustainable resource management**, ensuring long-term environmental and economic sustainability.

The category of digital applications has strict ties and overlaps with digital infrastructures (as discussed in Section 3.7.) and data (Section 3.2.). Here follows a small selection of examples of digital applications relevant for rural development that may be interesting for the six SMART ERA case studies. Some of these examples were proposed by pilot case studies themselves, during the exploratory workshop on digital enablers held at the consortium meeting in Mallorca in June 2024, as described in Annex D. The list of subcategories also includes types of digital applications provided by SMART ERA WP4 in the form of technological components already developed or experimented in previous projects by SMART ERA technical partners. These are highlighted in the text with the

SMART ERA logo ().

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Digital dashboards for data analysis and decision-making

Data dashboards are software tools designed to help users collect, process, analyse, and visualise data to gain insights, create models, and support informed decision-making. Dashboards can monitor the performance of various initiatives or projects over time. For example, a dashboard might display metrics related to crop yields, water usage, or economic indicators, allowing communities to assess the effectiveness of their strategies and adjust as necessary. In this way, dashboards also facilitate collaboration among different stakeholders because they provide a shared platform for data access. Community members, government agencies, and NGOs can all access the same data, promoting transparency and collective problem-solving.

Digital dashboards for territorial assessment

A special case of data dashboards is represented by digital tools purposefully aimed at integrating diverse datasets such as socio-economic, environmental, and demographic information, to create a comprehensive view of a region. They allow for the visualisation of critical metrics, including population density, employment rates, and access to services, through user-friendly charts, graphs, and maps that reveal trends and patterns. They may help identify priority domains, needs and challenges. In SMART ERA, these types of digital applications have an important role.

WP4, in collaboration with WP2, aims at designing and implementing the **SMART ERA data dashboard** for rural smartness assessment analysis of the needs of the project pilot areas, based on the SESAM methodology being developed within the project and described in deliverable D2.1.

Other types of dashboards experimented by partners in previous projects are for example:

The **Territorial Analyzer** proposed by SCCH that leverages data from Open Street map and generative AI algorithms to produce written reports with recommendations on how to improve the digitalisation level of a rural area.

The **Seroi+ Calculator**² proposed by UL which was successfully employed in different projects: Erudite and Erudite 2.0., EDIH 4PDIH, Carpe Digem, Public Link, Smart Agro Grape. It consists in a digital tool that measures the value of digital services considering social, environmental, and economic impacts

Territorial overviews developed by UL within the EDIH 4PDIH project³ is a tool offering data visualisation (for example on connectivity) that can be used for varied purposes of policy makers working on policy instruments. Originally tested for Slovenian municipalities, it provides an overview of priority domains, needs and challenges by using open data and SEROI+ methodology for mapping out the needs of Slovenian municipalities.

The **Territorial Digital assessment tool** was developed within the Interreg project Carpe Digem⁴. It allows stakeholders to establish digital maturity of territories

² <https://seroi.plus/>.

³ <https://4pdih.com/povezljivost-v-sloveniji/> and <https://4pdih.com/orodje/>.

⁴ carpedigem.eu.

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including peripheral and emerging territories to (further) develop and improve their digital transformation strategies. The tool consists of nine key dimensions that are related to both preconditions and accelerators of digital transformation of territories. Dimensions assessed are infrastructure, open data, digital education, attraction and retention of talent from the field of IT, digital competences of companies, digital innovation ecosystems, finance, support services and governance and leadership. For each dimension a scoring system from 1 – 5 was developed to indicate the current state of play. The tool generates a report, consisting of a visual diagram, accompanied with achieved levels of digital maturity for each of the listed dimensions.

Data ecosystem platforms

As a generalisation of data dashboards, data ecosystem platforms offer structured ways to discover, harmonise, synchronise and integrate multi-source data and deduct new information. They are essential to enable interoperability and standardisation of data exchange. These platforms may represent an essential prerequisite for implementing information services in complex data environments. In SMART ERA, technical partners have a solid background expertise in the development of this type of platforms and can offer ready-to-use solutions, like for example the following:

The **Digital Enabler** developed by ENG offers a complete pipeline for harvesting, integrating and digesting data, up to the fast reusable dashboards creation and management and fast web/mobile apps generation.

NADIA is ANYSOL’s Data and FIWARE based platform. It enables the collection of data from heterogeneous sources and formats, ensuring comprehensive data gathering. It standardises the collected data in smart data models, ensuring consistency and compatibility and facilitates the analysis and cross-referencing of standardised data, enhancing the depth and breadth of insights. It allows the visualisation of data using powerful visualisation tools, making complex data more accessible and understandable through dashboards.

Domain specific applications can be built on top of data ecosystem platforms, such as the **NADIA Smart Logistics** made available by ANYSOL that allows the creation of intelligent home delivery routes. The system calculates the shortest and most optimised route among all the defined delivery points. By optimising routes, trips are reduced, leading to lower energy consumption, which in turn reduces pollution and increases sustainability. Shorter trips also mean reduced delivery times, with increased benefit and satisfaction for the population in dispersed areas.

Digital Twins

Digital Twins can create virtual representations of physical objects or systems in rural settings, updating them with real-time data and using simulation, machine learning, and reasoning to aid decision-making and capacity building. By implementing this approach, rural areas can benefit from improved planning, control, and resource utilisation. For example, by integrating sensor networks and Earth observation data, digital twins create a comprehensive and real-time representation of **environmental conditions**. This advanced

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visualisation and analysis empower rural farmers to make informed, data-driven decisions, optimise resource allocation, and improve farm management practices for greater efficiency and sustainability. Digital twins can also simulate habitats and ecosystems, enabling the prediction of how environmental changes and human activities impact **biodiversity protection**.

An example of **Community Digital Twin (CDT)** is being developed by FBK as a platform tailored for capturing and analysing the complex dynamics of social or socio-technical systems. It is capable of performing complex analysis and prediction tasks. It has been tested in different domains: for mobility, to analyse traffic patterns and predict transportation needs; for tourism, to manage tourist flows and predict tourism trends; for civil protection, for emergency response planning and predicting and mitigating disaster impacts.

UL is also working on a **numerical predictive model to reduce the environmental impacts of agriculture** by means of a digital platform for data collection, processing, modelling and forecasting, based on environmental observations generated by field sensors.

Public deliberation platforms

Online deliberation platforms are digital tools designed to facilitate structured and equitable discussions among community members, allowing them to engage in decision-making processes. These platforms typically include features such as structured agendas to guide discussions, speaker management systems to ensure everyone has a chance to contribute, and automated moderation tools to maintain a respectful environment. They also offer real-time analytics to monitor conversations and have the scalability to support multiple discussion groups simultaneously.

As an example, **Decidim** is a multi-language open-source digital platform, made available by partner ENG, designed to support participatory and deliberative democracy⁵. Initially developed for the City of Barcelona, it helps governments and organisations involve citizens in decision-making processes, facilitating the creation and sharing of new ideas, needs and proposed solutions, the voting and commenting for ideas and proposals, the evaluation and selection of proposed ideas, the publication of posts, articles, blogs, meeting (physical/virtual) announcements and debates.

Web content management systems

A web content management system is a software application that allows users to create, edit, manage, and publish digital content on websites without needing extensive technical knowledge. These systems provide a user-friendly interface for managing various types of content, such as text, images, videos, and interactive elements. These types of platforms often include features like templates for consistent design, collaboration tools for team-based content creation, and automated workflows for content approval and publishing.

⁵ <https://decidim.org/about/>.

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As an example, **Egnition**, made available by partner MUNICIPIA, is a web content management system delivered in SaaS mode. It allows the management of the contents of a website (hypertext level) and apps supporting many different types of content through a single framework environment, like: audio, video, images, text, schedule and broadcast on monitor, lighting, holograms, projections. It includes a hierarchical authentication system with different types of users.

Wisita is an example of multimedia guide system, developed on top of the Egnition content management system, for managing tourist guides in both indoor and outdoor settings;

Participatory digital mapping

Participatory digital mapping describes various approaches and techniques that merge modern cartography tools with participatory methods to document and display the spatial knowledge of local communities. Typical applications are for example resource mapping and cultural heritage conservation, where geographically referenced information on natural resources, cultural points of interest and services like health posts, schools, water sources, museums and infrastructures are captured through participatory methods. This helps identify existing capacities and key gaps in rural areas.

Citizen science platforms

Citizen science platforms are online tools (web-based or apps for smartphones) and services that facilitate and support the participation of the general public in scientific research projects. By involving citizens in data collection and analysis, these tools empower communities to contribute to monitoring environmental conditions, biodiversity, and habitat conservation, as well as to collect information on traditional practices, such as sustainable agriculture and regional food systems. This might help ensure that local specificities are not lost over time.

Digital Storytelling

Digital storytelling allows the creation of a narrative using digital media such as video, audio, images, text and interactive elements. Digital storytelling empowers rural communities by providing a platform to share their voices and stories. It can, for example, promote local products by sharing the history, tradition, and unique qualities of local products, or it can document and preserve traditional farming methods and culinary practices, maintaining cultural heritage for future generations.

Digital geo-routes, mobile guides

As a complement to digital storytelling, digital geo-routes provide detailed maps and information on local attractions, services, and infrastructure. This improves accessibility and navigation for visitors, making it easier to engage with the local community and economy. They may support sustainable tourism by highlighting rural areas' natural resources, geological heritage, and cultural significance, as well as recommend slow tourism routes. Digital geo-routes may be implemented in the form of mobile guides.

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E-commerce platforms

E-commerce platforms are digital platforms that enable businesses to sell their products or services online, reducing reliance on intermediaries. This can lead to better pricing for consumers and increased revenue for local businesses. Companies can list their products or services, including descriptions, prices, and images; tools are available to manage orders and payments through gateways that facilitate secure transactions. In the rural domain e-commerce can favour, for example, the access to market to small agri-food producers or to rural hospitality, and it can support young entrepreneurs by providing them with opportunities to expand their customer base. E-commerce platforms can also support the specific case of business-to-business (B2B) commerce.

Blockchain applications for traceability

Digital systems for tracing goods and products can help ensure the authenticity and quality of products, which can be especially important in rural agricultural sectors. These systems may use blockchain's decentralised and transparent means to enhance the traceability and transparency of supply chains. By implementing blockchain, these systems track products from the point of origin to the consumer, providing detailed records of each step in the supply chain. This helps in reducing fraud, improving product safety, and building trust among consumers. In rural areas, where supply chains can be complex and fragmented, blockchain technology can streamline operations, reduce costs, and improve the livelihoods of farmers and producers by providing them with better access to markets and fairer prices.

SMART ERA partner UM has for example developed a blockchain-based system to implement **traceability along the entire food supply chain**, from farmers, going through logistics, food processors, distribution centres, retailers up to consumers.

Motivational systems for sustainable actions

Motivational systems leverage mechanisms stemming from the research field of serious games (Bassanelli et al. 2022) (e.g., narrative, visual metaphors, content personalization, achievement symbols, progress bars, missions, challenges) that foster a sense of accomplishment and achievement within the community of users (Bassanelli et al. 2024). They empower creativity and feedback, promote social influence and relatedness, and strengthen the sense of ownership (of the participant) and belonging (to the community) (Bucchiarone et al. 2023). Innovative features include the possibility of characterising the profile of the various stakeholders involved (e.g., demographic information, roles, interests, competences) and of personalising the recommended activities/behaviours as well as the motivational mechanisms (missions, challenges, call to actions) according to each specific participant's profile. This allows to promote and valorise each individual's contribution, depending on their role, needs and competences, as well as to showcase the collective community-level achievements. These systems can also be used to share the progress and results with other related communities or interested entities. Examples of motivational systems are the following:

Play&Go is a mobile application and related information system, made available by SMART ERA partner FBK, that supports the implementation of sustainable mobility actions and campaigns, which can be customised according to city-level

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mobility objectives and target users. The application aims at making the adoption of sustainable transportation enjoyable, inducing a significant and permanent change in mobility habits, measuring the achieved effects and the possible impact on the city, collecting mobility data useful to analyse mobility phenomena.

Kids Go Green, developed by FBK, is a game-based educational platform involving the whole school community (children, teachers, families) in a collective exploratory journey made of sustainable home-school trips. Children report their daily home-to-school trips and gain sustainable (virtual) kilometres that allow the whole group to proceed along thematic educational journeys prepared by their teachers. The solution has demonstrated a positive impact on reducing the usage of cars at the benefit of sustainable mobility solutions and persistence of change in habits in the long term.

E-learning platforms for capacity building

E-learning platforms for capacity building in rural areas are digital tools designed to enhance skills and knowledge in remote and underserved regions. These platforms leverage technology to overcome geographical barriers, providing access to educational resources that might otherwise be unavailable. They make educational content accessible through the internet, mobile devices, and offline resources, ensuring that even those with limited connectivity can benefit. By reducing the need for physical infrastructure and travel, e-learning platforms lower the costs associated with training and education, making it more feasible to provide high-quality education to a larger number of people. They offer flexible learning schedules, allowing individuals to learn at their own pace and according to their own schedules, which is particularly important for rural populations with varying work and family commitments. Focusing on building the capacity of individuals, these platforms can provide training in various skills such as agriculture, healthcare, entrepreneurship, and digital literacy, empowering rural populations and improving their livelihoods. They also facilitate collaboration and networking among learners, educators, and experts, leading to the sharing of knowledge and best practices, further enhancing the learning experience.

Platforms to access e-services of general interest

Digital platforms can make services of general interest (SGIs) more accessible to a wider audience, including those in remote or underserved areas, through mobile apps, websites, and other online tools. By digitising services, platforms reduce the time and effort required to access them, such as online appointment booking systems for healthcare services, which save users from long waiting times and streamline the process.

At the same time, automation and digital tools reduce administrative costs and improve resource allocation. They also enhance transparency by providing clear and accessible information about services, processes, and performance, helping to build trust and ensure fair and efficient service delivery. In the background, digital platforms collect and analyse data on how services are used, for decision makers to improve service delivery. Furthermore, digital platforms facilitate collaboration between different service providers and stakeholders, leading to more integrated and comprehensive service offerings, ensuring users receive holistic support.

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Platforms for digital economy services

A generalisation of platforms providing access to SGIs are platforms that support the digital economy for micro enterprises, professionals, and citizens in remote areas, as a way to bridge the gap between urban and rural access to services and opportunities. They function as aggregators of different functionalities.

For example, e-commerce functionalities enable small businesses to reach a global market, providing tools for online sales, marketing, and logistics, which help businesses in remote areas expand their customer base and increase revenue. They can also have a local scope, to improve the connection between local producers and local consumers. Financial services provide secure payment processing, micro-lending, and financial management services, which are vital for businesses in remote areas with limited access to traditional banking. Collaboration and communication tools facilitate remote work and collaboration, enabling professionals in remote areas to connect with colleagues and clients worldwide. Bespoke agricultural information services may offer tools and resources specifically designed for farmers and agricultural businesses. These services provide access to market information, weather forecasts, and farm management tools, helping farmers in remote areas optimise their operations and increase productivity.

3.5. Communication and training

Communication is fundamental to raising awareness, sharing knowledge, and facilitating the adoption of innovative practices, inputs, and technologies. Communication also fosters participatory approaches in the innovation process, allowing rural communities to voice their views, opinions, and interests, which are essential for developing and disseminating innovative practices and new technologies (Melaku et al, 2024). Communication and training may be needed at different times and for different purposes during the process; besides, activities can exploit different channels, ranging from traditional channels (e.g., paper-based communication) to digitally-enabled communication (e.g., social media channels).

This ingredient category can be further divided into several types of communication that can be exploited for different purposes at different stages of the project development. The following list is not exhaustive.

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Campaigns to raise awareness

Communication and awareness-raising campaigns help promote and facilitate the adoption of new ideas, technologies, and practices within rural communities. This encompasses not only the dissemination of information but also the engagement of community members in discussions that influence their practices and perceptions.

During the events, digital and traditional media can be mixed. For instance, attendees can be encouraged to share their experiences on social media during the event using a specific hashtag, fostering a sense of community and increasing visibility for the initiative.

Meetups

Meetups are informal gatherings of individuals with shared interests, often organised through online platforms, where participants come together to discuss, collaborate, and engage in activities related to those interests. These events range from casual social meetups to structured workshops or discussions on specific topics. They serve as a platform for community building and networking, connecting individuals from different sectors, fostering relationships and potential collaborations and strengthening local ties. Through knowledge sharing and skill development, workshops and presentations at meetups enhance community members' capabilities. Additionally, the exchange of best practices among farmers, entrepreneurs, and local leaders helps disseminate innovative solutions.

Continuous updates and feedback on results

Keeping stakeholders informed throughout rural development projects ensures transparency, fostering collaboration, and enhancing the effectiveness of initiatives (Sulaiman, 2023). Participants and stakeholders should be continuously updated on the outcomes of the different phases and ongoing activities.

Different channels can be exploited to update stakeholders and participants regularly: newsletters, local media and print channels, mobile outreach, dedicated websites, community meetings and workshops. Visual and multilingual communication, including local dialects, can ensure inclusivity and better understanding.

Training, capacity building and skills development

Training facilitates the adoption of new technologies, practices, or approaches introduced by the project. By providing hands-on training and demonstrating the benefits of innovations, projects can overcome resistance to change and encourage communities to embrace new ways of doing things.

Training contributes to the long-term sustainability of rural development projects by building the capacity of local institutions and service providers. By training local trainers and establishing linkages with existing extension systems, projects can ensure that communities continue to receive support even after the project ends.

Local product advertising

When developing communication strategies for local products in rural innovation projects, several factors should be considered to ensure effectiveness and community engagement. For example, engaging community members in creating and distributing messages ensures that contents resonate with local values and needs. Encouraging local artisans, farmers, and businesses to participate in crafting marketing narratives also improves authenticity and

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the sense of ownership of the initiative. Storytelling techniques can be used to convey the journey of local products from production to consumption, highlighting the people behind them. Engaging local "influencers" may help spread the message about local products through their networks. Communicating sustainable practices associated with local products, such as organic farming or fair trade principles, appeals to consumers who prioritise ethical consumption.

3.6. Incentives

Incentives are important to support long-term collaborative initiatives because they address fundamental human motivations and behaviours, fostering sustained engagement and commitment among participating parties. They can provide a sense of purpose, recognition, and satisfaction and sustain long-term motivation and engagement of people in their work or personal lives.

Incentivisation mechanisms can be categorised by the type of benefit they offer: immediate tangible rewards (such as money, gift cards, or gadgets, effective for data collection), potential future benefits (like discounts or networking opportunities, appealing for future business potential), social benefits (providing public recognition, awards, or visibility for contributions), and self-satisfaction (ensuring a positive atmosphere to encourage sustained participation over time).

Concrete, immediate benefit

These concrete goods can be used to reward participation, such as gadgets to thank for collaboration: physical gadgets (like a bag, pen, notebook, or powerbank) or merchandising material (such as a USB pen drive, t-shirts) can be offered to participants. Besides, small monetary rewards can be provided to individuals or organisations to encourage participation. For example, offering grants, tax incentives, or financial rewards for engaging in desired activities like volunteering, community service, or participating in public decision-making processes.

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Social benefit

There are different ways in which social benefits can be envisaged.

Appreciation and Acknowledgment: Expressing gratitude and recognizing the value of contributions can foster a sense of pride and accomplishment, encouraging continued participation. This can be put into practice, for example, by demonstrating appreciation and giving value to the collected feedback during a collaborative activity or by demonstrating progress made based on past input/effort.

Publicly acknowledging the contributions and efforts of individuals or organisations: This can be done through formal or informal channels, such as public meetings, events, newsletters, or social media platforms.

Testimonials and Case Studies: Sharing success stories and testimonials that highlight the impact of collaborative activities can inspire others to get involved. This form of social recognition demonstrates the value of participation and showcases the positive outcomes that can be achieved through collaboration.

Self-satisfaction and enjoyment

A positive atmosphere and enjoyment during collaborative activities are considered powerful incentives. Enjoyment and fun sustain commitment and the opportunity to network and meet new people. This can be achieved in different ways, for instance, by organising a friendly contest for professional training, with participants divided into small teams, by organising refreshments during events or ice-breaking activities to connect participants.

Potential future benefits

Participants can also be incentivized by focusing on their future benefits and leveraging the existing interests of participants. For instance, vouchers for future benefits (e.g., vouchers for discounts, benefits at cafeteria and bookshop), or networking and community building. By facilitating connections among individuals engaged in collaborative activities, public administration can create a community where participants can exchange ideas, share experiences, and receive peer support.

Gamification and Challenges

Introducing gamification and challenges into rural innovation initiatives can significantly enhance community engagement, participation, and overall effectiveness. Introducing gamification elements, such as competitions, challenges, or leaderboards, can make participation more engaging and enjoyable. By setting goals, providing rewards for achievements, and fostering healthy competition, individuals can be motivated to actively participate. This can make participation more attractive, motivate individuals and communities to strive for excellence, and ultimately lead to more sustainable and impactful outcomes.

3.7. Hardware and digital infrastructure

Digital Infrastructure refers to the combination of hardware, networks, and data centres that enable the functioning of digital services, including elements such as physical (fiber-optic cables) and virtual networks. Digital infrastructure is essential for enabling businesses and communities to operate efficiently in a connected world, supporting everything from communication to data processing and service delivery. Reliable digital infrastructure ensures connectivity, enabling rural communities to access online resources, engage in e-commerce, and leverage tools like precision agriculture and telehealth services.

Technical infrastructure for communication services

Technical infrastructure for communication services encompasses the systems and technologies that support effective communication and data exchange. It includes hardware components like routers, switches, servers, and cables, which form the physical backbone of networks, as well as telecommunication technologies such as fiber optics, satellites, and wireless systems that enable connectivity. An efficient communication infrastructure allows rural residents to access essential e-services, such as e-government platforms, telehealth, and online education, improving their quality of life and access to resources. It also facilitates remote work, enabling individuals to work for companies or clients outside their immediate area. New economic models such as e-commerce, digital marketing, and online marketplaces for local products strongly rely on the communication infrastructure.

IoT sensor networks

These networks rely on infrastructure that supports various types of sensors, enabling real-time monitoring and data collection. Examples of applications to the rural settings include:

- **IoT sensors for agriculture.** Sensors can measure soil moisture, temperature, humidity, nutrient levels, and crop health, providing farmers with precise insights to optimise their practices. Studies such as those by Xu et al. (2022) and Wang et al.

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(2006) highlight the potential of IoT technologies in transforming traditional farming into a data-driven enterprise, which is more attractive to younger generations.

- **IoT sensors for environmental risk prevention** can enhance safety and environmental protection in rural areas. By utilising infrastructure that supports sensors for monitoring risks such as landslides and water quality, these networks provide real-time data that can predict and mitigate potential hazards (Vijayakumar and Ramya, 2015; Mei et al., 2019). These technologies contribute to a safer living environment, promoting sustainable practices and improving overall environmental resilience.
- **IoT sensors for resource management.** By monitoring water usage, energy consumption, and environmental conditions, IoT networks help rural areas implement sustainable practices. This reduces costs and ensures the longevity of natural resources, fostering eco-friendly innovations.
- **IoT to monitor fauna.** Radio collars equipped with GPS or other sensors can collect data on animals (such as the animal’s location, movement, and behaviour) and transmit it to a central system for analysis. This practice helps protect biodiversity but also increases the safety of local communities and tourists, in the case of monitoring large carnivores.
- **Movable IoT sensor networks.** Movable IoT infrastructures allow for the reusability of expensive and complex networked sensors, making advanced technologies more accessible to rural communities. For example, an itinerant van equipped with sensors can travel to different locations, enabling real-time data collection and monitoring for agricultural, environmental, or infrastructure purposes. This approach reduces the need for permanent infrastructure investments, maximises the use of costly equipment, and ensures that sensor networks are deployed efficiently, responding to immediate needs without the high costs of establishing fixed installations.

Drones

Drones equipped with cameras, sensors and spraying capabilities can provide mapping and analysis of soil, crops and livestock, as well as precision monitoring of plant health, water usage, and pest/disease detection. Other applications of interest for rural areas are: disaster management (floods, wildfires, missing persons...), delivery services, inspection of remote infrastructure, conservation (monitoring of wildlife and environment), mapping and surveying (topographical maps for land management, forestry and/or urban development), but also for telecommunication (in remote areas, drones can help establish provisional communication networks).

Remote satellite sensing

Remote satellite sensing is the process of using satellites equipped with sensors to collect data about the Earth's surface and atmosphere without physical contact. This technology captures images and measurements, such as temperature, vegetation, and land use, which are used for various applications like environmental monitoring, agriculture, and disaster management.

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Wearable biosensors for livestock

These devices can enhance agricultural practices because they provide real-time monitoring of animal health and behaviour, enabling farmers to make informed decisions that enhance productivity and sustainability (Lee and Seo, 2021).

3.8. Physical infrastructure and equipment

Physical infrastructure and equipment in rural areas refer to the tangible assets and facilities that support various functions essential for community development, quality of life and capacity to stay. Examples include emergency management facilities, transportation networks, public safety systems, and structures designed for wildlife coexistence.

Physical infrastructure for emergency management

Physical infrastructure for emergency management encompasses the tangible assets that support the preparedness, response, recovery, and mitigation of emergencies and disasters. This infrastructure includes a wide range of components that enable effective emergency management operations and enhance community resilience against various hazards, like for example helicopter landing zones, evacuation plans and means, public safety communication spectrum, firebreak paths⁶.

Physical infrastructures for coexistence between humans and wild fauna

These refer to the physical and organisational systems designed to facilitate harmonious interactions between human populations and wildlife. These infrastructures aim to minimise conflicts, enhance safety, and promote sustainable practices that allow both humans and wildlife to live side by side in shared environments. They include electric fences (used for example against bears, wolves, wild boars), secured waste bins, wildlife crossings, and anti-crossing deterrents. Although not relevant in all rural areas, physical infrastructures of this type are for example important in the Val di Sole case study.

⁶ https://www.cisa.gov/sites/default/files/publications/NECP_Spotlight_REMCDP_12.07.2020_508C.pdf

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Infrastructures for transportation and mobility

These refer to the physical and organisational systems that enable the movement of people, goods, and services. These include roads, bridges, railways, and public transportation networks, as well as supporting facilities like terminals, bike lanes, and pedestrian pathways.

Equipment for transportation innovation

In rural areas where public transport may be limited, alternative forms of transport may be required to support the local population and temporary visitors.

For example, on-demand transport services adapt to the specific needs of users, providing on-demand shuttles or community transport schemes that respond to local demand. They enhance access to essential services and offer flexibility in travel schedules.

Affordable bicycles, electric bikes (e-bikes), electric scooters provide instead an eco-friendly transportation option for short distances. These can reduce carbon emissions and be also appealing for tourists. They require an appropriate distributed infrastructure with recharge stations.

Physical infrastructure and equipment for energy production and water supply

Tangible systems, facilities, and technologies are required for generating, distributing, and utilising renewable energy sources. This infrastructure encompasses a wide range of components necessary for the effective transition from fossil fuels to sustainable energy systems, like for example photovoltaic panels and wind turbines, independent energy sources for remote locations (Díaz and van Vliet, 2018), lagoons for natural water storage (Viviroli et al., 2011).

Agricultural equipment

Types of equipment and tools may be varied and include innovative agricultural machinery like precision farming tractors, as well as low-cost harvesting tools for small-scale farmers, but also efficient watering systems (like drip irrigation) or composting systems to produce bio-fertilisers.

Physical spaces

Another important ingredient for rural innovation, that is essential when planning social innovations based on services that enhance community well-being, facilitate economic growth, and promote social cohesion, is the availability of appropriate physical spaces to host activities or co-living.

- **Business hubs:** Physical spaces such as co-working centres, business incubators, and marketplaces provide entrepreneurs with the resources and support needed to start and grow their businesses. This fosters local economic development and job creation (Akhavan et al., 2022).
- **Public gathering spaces:** parks, community centres, and event venues serve as gathering places for residents to socialise, participate in community events, and engage in civic activities. These interactions strengthen social ties and promote a sense of belonging.

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- **Community facilities and services.** Physical spaces such as schools, and libraries can provide essential services to rural residents. Access to quality health care and education improves the overall quality of life and helps retain residents in rural areas.
- **Community multifunctional spaces.** Multifunctional spaces offer versatile environments that foster collaboration, creativity, and resource sharing. They serve as hubs where community members can access shared resources such as meeting rooms, technology, and tools. This accessibility encourages collaboration among local entrepreneurs, farmers, artisans, and organisations.
- **Co-housing solutions** promote the creation of shared living environments where residents can interact, collaborate, and support one another. Moreover, co-housing allows for the sharing of resources such as tools, vehicles, and communal facilities (e.g., kitchens, gardens). This reduces individual costs and promotes sustainable consumption practices.
- **Single point of access to services:** By providing a single point of access to various services and resources, residents can easily obtain information and services related to healthcare, education, social services, and local government⁷. This reduces the complexity and time required to navigate multiple service providers.

3.9. Political enablers

Political enablers comprise the actions, policies, and institutional arrangements that can facilitate rural innovation. These enablers can include supportive legislation, funding mechanisms, and collaborative networks that bring together different actors in the innovation ecosystem. Governments can facilitate access to resources, networking opportunities, and training programs while encouraging collaboration among stakeholders, including local

⁷ <https://www.ufficiostampa.provincia.tn.it/Comunicati/Contributi-ai-multiservizi-nelle-zone-di-montagna-premiati-gli-esercizi-che-erogano-maggiori-servizi-alla-popolazione>.

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authorities, businesses, and educational institutions. A multi-level governance approach ensures that policies harness the unique strengths of various actors, fostering capacity building and enabling community-led innovation. Policy audits and participatory governance further ensure that strategies reflect local needs and priorities, enhancing their effectiveness and relevance (Georgios, 2023).

Political advocacy

For an initiative to gain long-term viability and impact, it requires approval or support from policymakers. Political advocacy helps align the initiative with public policy objectives, mobilises institutional support, and ensures that it can continue to operate within the legal and regulatory frameworks. Political endorsement is key in translating local or bottom-up community efforts into lasting change. Combining top-down advocacy with bottom-up local community involvement is considered a powerful strategy for supporting rural development (OECD, 2014). This dual approach leverages the strengths of both methods to create a more effective and inclusive framework for innovation and growth in rural areas. Top-down advocacy ensures that broader policy goals and frameworks are established, while bottom-up involvement brings local knowledge and specific needs into the decision-making process. This integration helps create policies fit to local contexts, fostering a sense of ownership among community members.

Governmental authorities can influence rural entrepreneurship by creating supportive environments. This includes providing resources, facilitating networking, and ensuring policies are accessible and relevant to local needs. As highlighted in the research by Kujala et al. (2021), trust, discretion, creativity, and learning are critical factors that allow rural authorities to act as effective enablers of entrepreneurship.

Political endorsement can be achieved through several strategies, such as building partnerships with stakeholders like businesses and NGOs, engaging in lobbying and advocacy, aligning the initiative with current policy priorities, and mobilising grassroots support to apply bottom-up pressure and raising public awareness through media and public discourse can further sway political opinion.

Multi-level governance and community engagement

Governance in the context of rural innovation refers to the frameworks and processes through which decisions are made and implemented regarding rural development initiatives. It encompasses the interactions among various stakeholders, including government entities, local communities, businesses, and civil society organisations.

There are different types of governance models: they can be **top-down approaches**, where policies are formulated at higher levels of government, and **bottom-up strategies** that empower local communities to take an active role in decision-making processes (as presented in Section 2.1). Hybrid approaches combine elements of both top-down and bottom-up strategies to maximise their strengths while mitigating weaknesses. For instance, while top-down policies can provide necessary resources and frameworks for innovation, bottom-up engagement ensures that these initiatives are grounded in local realities and address concrete local needs.

Participatory governance is a model that actively involves local communities in decision-making processes, ensuring that policies and initiatives reflect their specific needs and priorities. This bottom-up approach is particularly effective in rural areas, where unique

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challenges and opportunities require tailored solutions that are best understood by the residents themselves (Georgios, 2023).

A **multi-layer structure** emphasises instead the distribution of powers across various levels of government (national, regional, intermediate and local). Rather than following a strict hierarchical order, it operates on a principle of interdependence, where each level and actor contributes unique resources and skills (Mantino, 2005).

Capacity building

Capacity building refers to actions that enhance the skills, knowledge, and resources necessary for effective governance and community engagement. It involves efforts and actions to improve the capabilities of individuals, organisations, and institutions, enabling them to better address local challenges and to actively participate in decision-making processes. As suggested by Cuthill and Fien (2005) building the capacity of local citizens to take collaborative action amplifies participation, empowerment, and civil engagement.

Capacity building can be achieved, for instance, by developing **training and education programs**: political enablers can facilitate access to training programs that equip local entrepreneurs with the skills needed for innovation. Besides, knowledge transfer initiatives can be encouraged through partnerships between educational institutions and rural businesses.

Policy audit

SMART ERA has already developed, in Task 6.1, guidelines that will enable pilot responsible partners to analyse the key policy frameworks and the initiatives, strategies and instruments in their national and regional contexts (with a particular emphasis on EU-supported policies) that are enablers/disablers of community-led innovation in rural areas.

Guidelines provide a simplified set of steps of **actor-centred policy analysis** that can be directly used by the SMART ERA communities to (1) identify issues, (2) identify actors connected to the issue, (3) analyse the actors' respective positions, opportunities and barriers, and finally (4) build policy options, alternative scenarios and reporting.

This is an ongoing work conducted in WP6. Future work will extrapolate information from these activities and create material to be inserted in the categorization of SIP ingredients and in the SIP Co-design Toolkit materials.

3.10. Financial and economic enablers

Financial and economic enablers determine the feasibility and long-term success of initiatives and sustainability of implemented services.

Access to funding, whether through grants, subsidies, or investment opportunities, ensures that innovative projects can be implemented and scaled effectively. Economic enablers, such as tax incentives, microfinance programs, and market access support, create an environment where businesses can do well.

Funding

Funding is a critical component, as rural areas often lack the necessary capital to invest in modern infrastructure, technology, and business development. Government grants, EU structural funds, and private investments may provide essential financial support to rural projects. Finding and managing funding for rural innovation requires a strategic approach that includes identifying diverse funding sources, building partnerships, developing competitive proposals, and ensuring effective fund management.

Understanding and planning rural markets

Understanding the market context is critical to ensuring that innovative ideas are tailored to the specific needs and opportunities of rural regions. Rural innovators must account for the unique economic structures, such as smaller market sizes and dispersed populations, which can shape the demand for new products and services (Mahroum et al., 2007).

Business models

Specific resources for developing business models in SMART ERA will be implemented in Task 3.4 "Business models for SIPs" (M19-M42). This task is about creating new business models to ensure the sustainability of each SIP with the help of project partners. Business Model Canvas (BMC) will be used to look at various aspects like governance, key activities, resources needed, value propositions, target audiences, customer relations, channels, and financial structures.

3.11. Legal aspects

Considering the legal ingredient in innovation activities ensures the compliance with laws and the protection of stakeholders' rights. Well-defined contractual agreements, including partnership and service agreements, clarify roles and responsibilities, preventing disputes and enhancing accountability throughout the project. For initiatives that involve the development and deployment of digital services, understanding data usage laws and ensuring GDPR compliance ensure sustainability and community trust. Legal aspects, especially when the use of ICT is involved, should be considered during the design, development, and deployment phases to ensure compliance and to protect stakeholders. Sample subcategories are the following.

Regulatory compliance

Projects must consider local, regional, national and European laws governing the sectors addressed in rural innovation initiatives, such as agriculture, food processing, tourism, renewable energy, transportation and health. Specific regulations should be scouted for each local context and type of innovation solution to rural challenges.

GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation)

The GDPR is a European Union regulation focused on safeguarding individuals' privacy by enforcing standards for managing personal data responsibly and transparently.

Compliance with GDPR is essential for projects that involve collecting or processing data about rural populations or stakeholders. It ensures that data-driven ICT solutions respect privacy, fostering trust and enabling broader community engagement. Checklists are available to facilitate compliance with the regulation⁸.

⁸ <https://gdprinfo.eu/gdpr-checklist>.

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Contractual Agreements

A contractual agreement is a legally binding document that outlines the terms and conditions of a relationship between two or more parties. These agreements establish clear roles and responsibilities, thereby minimising the potential for disputes. They can consist in **partnership agreements**, when there is a formal collaboration between organisations or stakeholders that need to agree contributions and expectations, or in **service agreements** when external services (such as consultancy or technology providers) are involved, to define deliverables and timelines.

EU AI ACT

The EU AI Act is a pioneering regulatory framework for the development and use of Artificial Intelligence within the European Union⁹. It focuses on ensuring AI systems are safe, ethical, and non-discriminatory. All AI technologies deployed in rural areas, such as predictive analytics for agriculture or remote healthcare solutions, must align with this act.

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

IPR covers patents, copyrights, trademarks, appellations of origin, and design rights, offering legal protections for innovative creations and intellectual assets¹⁰. Protecting innovations specific to rural contexts, such as local products or traditional knowledge, allows communities to maintain ownership and control over their unique resources and services, creating economic opportunities.

Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs)

PPPs can act as legal enablers for rural innovation. By facilitating collaboration between government entities and private sector companies, PPPs create a structured framework through which both parties can pool resources, share risks, and harness the strengths of each sector to promote rural development and innovation.

3.12. Smartness assessment of the territory

A special category of ingredients for rural innovation is represented by methods that allow rural areas to assess their territorial smartness along different dimensions, both to analyse their starting point and help stakeholders acquire knowledge on the potential and priorities of their area during the problem definition phase, as well as to perform impact evaluation after the interventions. As mentioned in previous Section 3.4 on digital applications, there exist digital dashboards for smartness assessment implementing data collection and visualization functionalities in support of methods for the smartness assessment of a territory. However, not all methodologies have a digital counterpart.

Task 2.1 in SMART ERA workplan performed an extensive research on existing smartness assessment methods, employed in rural contexts. Some of them focus on economic aspects, others on policies, or on agriculture; others consider different dimensions at the same time. Starting from this background research, a bespoke multi-dimensional

⁹ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/en/article/20230601STO93804/eu-ai-act-first-regulation-on-artificial-intelligence>.

¹⁰ https://policy.trade.ec.europa.eu/enforcement-and-protection/protecting-eu-creations-inventions-and-designs_en.

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methodology was developed (named SESAM) that merges different assessment dimensions (enabling factors, mobility and transport, economy, smart governance and policy, services of general interest, environment and environmental and climate-related SDGs) and that combines qualitative and quantitative measures.

The research work from Task 2.1 is documented in Deliverable 2.1 (delivered at M12) and will be used as the basis for the creation of contents to complement the SIP ingredients categorisation in this area and the materials of SIP Co-design Toolkit.

4. SIP Co-design Toolkit: supporting rural areas in defining their SIPs

Each of the six SMART ERA pilot communities will experiment with the co-creation of a SIP, going through all the phases of SIP co-design (within T3.3), "ingredients" implementation (WP4), actual delivery and evaluation of the solution (T5.3) and business model creation for the sustainability of the innovation (T3.4).

The ultimate output of this SIP collaborative design and development process will be:

**a reasoned set of
SIP ingredients**

+

**a detailed description of the
solution components and
insights into their application**

This expected output needs to serve multiple purposes:

- Provide **common ground** to assist the collaborative processes and transparent communication within the network of stakeholders participating in the process.
- **Document** what was done to allow local communities to replicate the solutions at a larger scale or reuse the co-production approach for future initiatives, strengthening their innovation capacity.
- Help **disseminate** and inspire other communities.
- **Explain** which ingredients may be necessary to implement a solution to a particular rural challenge, barriers, lessons learned and implications to support replicability.

Figure 9 shows how the **SIP detailed description** will progressively be assembled. The co-design phase (highlighted in orange in the figure) is addressed in detail in WP3 and is studied in this chapter.

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Figure 9. Flow of information that will populate the SIP description along the process

In the initial stages of **SIP co-design**, pilots will be able to describe in a brief and focused way the context and specificity of the rural challenge considered, the pilot area for which the solution was developed and the initial set of ingredients identified during the co-design activities. (For rural areas already partners of the SMART ERA consortium, an initial draft of parts of this information was included in Deliverable 5.1). During the SIP co-design activities (coordinated by T3.3 and performed in WP5), pilots will progressively identify a list of ingredients that synergically contribute to solving their rural challenge. These ingredients will populate the visual representation of the SIP and the description template. During the **ingredients implementation phase** (WP4), it is expected that further information will arise related to technical requirements and constraints, as well as the costs and limitations of ingredients. The actual **deployment and evaluation** (within Task 5.3) of the designed SIP are expected to produce information on the actual impact of the SIP and lessons learned for its realisation that are worth documenting. The business models arising from Task 3.4 will enrich the SIP description with insights into **sustainability and replicability**.

The following sections of this chapter describe resources developed in T3.1 to **support the SIP co-design phase** and collected in the so-called "**SIP Co-design Toolkit**".

4.1. Overview of the analogue SIP Co-design Toolkit

The SIP Co-design Toolkit has been conceived to support rural communities during the co-design of their SIP along different dimensions:

- **Empowerment and capacity building:** The toolkit offers inspiring material, guidelines and checklists that help pilots follow a reasoned process for selecting the ingredients of SIPs.
- **Guidance and Standardisation:** The toolkit provides a common template of fields and annotations that tell how the SIP should be described, including insights for reusability and facilitating search and inspiration.
- **Motivation:** Digital functionalities associated with the toolkit will implement motivational mechanisms to sustain participation and contribution.

The operative definition for SIP discussed in previous Section 2.5 also imposes specific requirements on the Co-design Toolkit to support SIPs creation. The fact that a SIP may be created in an incremental way, with complementary subparts, with adaptations needed for replicability, etc., implies that **there is no one rigid SIP co-design process** that may fit all use cases. For this reason:

- The co-design toolkit should guarantee **flexibility of use** to accommodate different design journeys and paces.
- The toolkit **does not have the ambition to be exhaustive**, i.e. to include all possible examples of ingredients. It aims, instead, at offering **a methodology to categorise and exemplify ingredients** that toolkit users can extend with their own ideas as necessary.
- The toolkit will be a **living resource** that will be iteratively refined and integrated with material developed in other SMART ERA work packages during the course of the project. For example, examples of business model canvases (T3.4), questionnaires for the smartness assessment of a territory (WP2) or guidelines extracted from policy audits (WP6) will become concrete sample ingredients to be added to the toolkit.

The SIP Co-design Toolkit is composed of five main parts:

- 1) A **SIP DESCRIPTION TEMPLATE** to be filled in with the detailed description of the SIP being created.
- 2) A **SIP BOARD**: a visual representation of the ingredients being assembled; it allows the progressive and iterative monitoring of the process outcome and facilitates documentation.
- 3) Materials to build capacity and stimulate reflection on different types of SIP ingredients.

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- a) **INGREDIENT CARDS** that describe examples of ingredients useful for innovation in rural areas. They are organised in categories for easier use.
 - b) **REFLECTION CARDS AND HOW-TOS** containing checklists or reflection questions that help reflect on each category of ingredients in its entirety (helpful for focused discussions).
- 4) **SUPPORT CANVASES** to facilitate specific activities and stimulate reflection on the process and cross-ingredient dependencies.
 - 5) Other **METHODOLOGICAL RESOURCES** for stakeholders' capacity building.

4.2. SIP description template

In the next phases of SMART ERA project development, a detailed description of how each use case unfolds, which co-design activities are organised to assemble the six pilot SIPs, how SIPs are validated, and which business models are adopted will be included in dedicated deliverables within WP5, T3.3 and T3.4.

The **SIP description** mentioned here serves a different purpose: it will consist of a compact summary of the relevant facts related to a SIP that needs to serve the goal of **communicating** what was done, **inspiring** other communities, providing essential information on the used SIP ingredients to help **build capacity** in other communities, and facilitating the **replication** of the process. At the current stage of project development, an initial SIP description template has been defined as illustrated in the table below, which will be further refined and integrated as new information needs emerge during the development of tasks T3.3 (dealing with the actual co-design of SIPs, in months M13-M36), T4.3 (dealing with SIPs' technological components development, in months M13-M36), T3.4 (reasoning with SIPs' business models, in months M19-M42), and T5.3 (deploying the SIPs in context and validating them, M25-M42).

Table 2. SIP description Template.

TITLE OF SIP
A recognisable name for identifying the SIP <i>Example: "SIP for on-demand mobility: Bus & Go"</i>
DESCRIPTION
A brief description of what the SIP is <i>Example: Package of ingredients necessary for implementing a service that offers on-demand mobility support to tourists and local population.....</i>
CHALLENGE ADDRESSED

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<p>Explanation of the rural challenge that originated the SIP</p> <p><i>Example: There was a need for an additional public transportation service with flexible management of routes and timetables, with special attention to the needs of disabled people, that is cheaper for the local administration and better solves mobility issues in a dispersed territory.</i></p> <p>.....</p>
<p>DIMENSIONS OF INNOVATION (as set out in the SESAM smartness assessment methodology)</p>
<p>Which aspects of your rural territory and community do you wish to innovate?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Enabling factors (You wish to improve digital infrastructure and literacy) <input type="checkbox"/> Mobility (You wish to discover new, smart, integrated forms of transportation) <input type="checkbox"/> Governance and Policies (You wish to improve public services, increase their efficiency, improve community leadership, explore possibilities for mobile working, etc.) <input type="checkbox"/> Economy (You wish to discover new and innovative modes/strategies to approach business development, for example, in the agri-food, tourism, energy production and other sectors) <input type="checkbox"/> Environment and climate-related SDGs (You wish to discover innovative and smart ways to enhance sustainable and smart approaches for local territory and environment, in compliance with sustainable development goals) <input type="checkbox"/> Services (You wish to create services of general interest, SGIs, and other local services) <input type="checkbox"/> Living (You wish to find innovative approaches/ solutions to improve general quality of life) <input type="checkbox"/> People (You wish to discover and stimulate approaches that promote (social) innovation and are inclusive of the whole society)
<p>CONTEXT IN WHICH THE SIP WAS DEVELOPED</p>
<p>Description of the place where the SIP was created and tested.</p> <p>Country: Region: Place: Population affected: Type of region:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> rural <input type="checkbox"/> mountain <input type="checkbox"/> suburban <input type="checkbox"/> coastal <input type="checkbox"/> lake <input type="checkbox"/> other <p><i>Example</i> <i>Country: Italy</i> <i>Region: Autonomous Province of Trento</i> <i>Place: network of municipalities Riva del Garda, Arco, Nago-Torbole</i> <i>Population affected: 38,379 inhabitants</i> <i>Type of region: lake</i></p>
<p>PERIOD OF SIP EXPERIMENTATION</p>

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<p>When the SIP was deployed and actually tested.</p> <p><i>Example</i> The Bus & Go service was launched in 2022 and was active for a pilot period from July to September. Since 2022, the service has been activated each year from late Spring to early Autumn.</p>
<p>WHO INITIATED THE PROCESS</p>
<p>From whom the initial ideas came from.</p> <p><i>Example: a group of citizens contacted the local municipal administration with a request to extend the public transportation service to areas currently not served appropriately. The request also included concerns about the accessibility of mobility services by vulnerable categories.</i></p>
<p>WHO COORDINATED THE PROCESS</p>
<p>Who took the lead of the initiative.</p> <p><i>Example: A core working group was established, including the mayors of the three municipalities, the local councillors for mobility, a representative of the local tourist organisation and a representative of the transport company already serving the area.</i></p>
<p>TYPES OF STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGED</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Governmental and administrative public Bodies <input type="checkbox"/> Local Communities <input type="checkbox"/> Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and local associations <input type="checkbox"/> Academic and Research Institutions <input type="checkbox"/> Private Sector and Entrepreneurs <input type="checkbox"/> Innovation brokers and facilitators <input type="checkbox"/> Experts and professionals
<p>DESCRIPTION OF STAKEHOLDERS</p>
<p>Description of stakeholders (their function and role) who contributed to the SIP creation process</p>
<p>VISUAL SUMMARY OF SIP</p>
<p>The SIP at a glance</p> <p><i>Example</i></p>

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SIP INGREDIENT

Description of the ingredient

Short description:

Category:

Phase in which is needed:

How it was obtained:

What it does:

Limitations:

Related costs:

Requirements and constraints for its use:

Example

Short description: Minibus with 19 seats

Category: Equipment

Phase in which is needed: The bus was rented for the periods of service delivery

How it was obtained: The bus was rented by the municipality of Riva del Garda from a local private company specialised in selling and renting vehicles

What it does: The minibus is used to connect existing bus stops in a flexible way, according to an itinerary computed according to booking requests

Limitations:

Related costs: Monthly paid rent

Requirements and constraints for its use: The size of the bus was determined by considering the expected average number of requests and the areas where the bus needed to go through. To reduce emissions in the historical centre, an electric

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<i>vehicle was used.</i>
+ SIP INGREDIENT
Description of the ingredient, following the schema above
+ ... other ingredients.....
Description of the ingredient, following the schema above
LESSONS LEARNED DURING THE SIP CREATION PROCESS
Description of aspects (for example, type of difficult decisions) that required some reasoning during the SIP creation process and how these aspects were tackled. This information may be useful when replicating the usage of the SIP. <i>Example: Initially, it was difficult to estimate the correct size of the bus. For this reason, it was decided to initiate the experimental phase of the service with a rented vehicle instead of immediately proceeding with a purchase.</i>
LESSONS LEARNED DURING THE SIP USE
Description of aspects that emerged during the use of the SIP and how these aspects may be used to improve the deployed innovation. This information may be useful when replicating the usage of the SIP. <i>Example: Statistics showed that a significant portion of users were local residents. This aspect suggests that the service could be extended for longer periods during the year.</i>
SUMMARY OF RESULTS OF SIP VALIDATION
Description of how the community received the innovation and the type of validation performed. <i>Example: The Bus & Go service was launched in 2022 and was active for a pilot period from July to September. During the validation period, the service registered 3.459 booking requests. Residents accounted for 60% of total users. The average age of users was 58. A satisfaction questionnaire was distributed to evaluate the perceived usability, usefulness and future intention to use the service.....</i>
BUSINESS MODEL FOR THE SIP
Description of how the innovation supported by the SIP was economically sustainable.
IMPACT OF THE SIP
Description of the benefits or disadvantages that were observed after the deployment of the SIP.

4.3. How to use the toolkit

The SIP Co-design Toolkit aims to **improve the local community’s capacity** to tackle innovation processes by providing tools and resources, such as cards, reflection questions and canvases, **for reflecting on the various “ingredients” involved in an innovation process.**

It is important to stress that the SIP Co-design Toolkit has not been conceived to provide a general step-by-step guide to collaborative design activities. In this sense, it doesn't replace already existing and well-validated co-design methodologies, like, for example, the general Double Diamond approach to design¹¹, the Design Thinking framework¹², the Values-led Participatory Design (Iversen et al., 2012), or other more specific methodologies guiding participatory rural innovation processes, as the ones produced by the Smart Villages project¹³ or the SEROI+ method developed within the ERUDITE project¹⁴. These **existing methodologies already suggest (flexible) sequences of phases** to frame the problem context, explore the problem space and define a specific challenge to solve (as was done in SMART ERA WP5 during the first year of project development), develop ideas for possible solutions, prototype and converge towards a solution to be delivered and tested.

Instead, the SIP Co-design Toolkit offers complementary resources specifically tailored to reason about the different ingredients of rural innovation and support the development of the SIP pivotal concept.

This means that the resources in the SIP Co-design Toolkit can be used in conjunction with different methodological frameworks (Double Diamond, Design Thinking, Values-led Participatory Design, SEROI+, ...) to facilitate specific activities involving rural communities and can be adapted to various contexts, from more institutional settings to more informal ones.

Within task T3.3, starting at month 13 of the SMART ERA project work plan, a plan for co-design workshops and activities will be set out that **combine participatory design steps with the SIP Co-design Toolkit resources** to validate with use cases the SMART ERA SIP-based approach to innovation.

During the SIP creation process, the SIP Co-design Toolkit will be used in different phases and for various purposes according to the needs of each pilot area.

4.3.1. Different users, flexible use

Who will use the SIP Co-design Toolkit? There will be primary and secondary users.

¹¹ <https://www.designcouncil.org.uk/our-resources/the-double-diamond/> (last accessed on the 14th of November 2024).

¹² <https://www.ideo.com/pages/design-thinking>, definition of Design Thinking by IDEO (last accessed on the 14th of November 2024).

¹³ <https://smartvillages.si/> (last accessed on the 14th of November 2024).

¹⁴ <https://seroi.plus/about/> (last accessed on the 14th of November 2024).

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Primary user: the facilitator(s)

<< A primary user is the main individual for whom a product or service is designed and who interacts with it directly. This user typically has the most frequent or intensive engagement with the product. >>

The primary user of the SIP Co-design Toolkit is the facilitator: a person or a team with expertise in mediation and collaborative processes who oversees co-design activities. They guide and manage the interactions and dynamics within a group to ensure inclusive participation. Their role is to create a supportive environment where diverse perspectives are heard, ideas can flow, and participants can co-create solutions. They also ensure that the group remains focused on shared goals defined by the SMART ERA partners.

Facilitators decide how to use the SMART ERA resources according to some considerations: the goal of the activity, the setting (formal, informal), participants' expertise, and time constraints.

Secondary users: stakeholders and local community

<< Secondary users are individuals or groups interacting with a product or service less frequently or indirectly than primary users. Secondary users often benefit from the product's features or outputs but may have different usage patterns, priorities, or goals than primary users. >>

The secondary users of the SIP Co-design Toolkit are the stakeholders and other actors participating in the co-design process, such as mayors of municipalities, representatives of local supply chains, associations, and local groups. Their experience with the toolkit is mediated by the facilitator.

4.3.2. User scenarios, tutorial and training

The materials of the SIP Co-design Toolkit can be used very flexibly by different users and for various purposes.

- **Preparation (before activities):** The toolkit may support the facilitator(s) to become aware of the different “ingredients” that should be considered. The facilitator can use the toolkit to prepare the presentations or co-design activities and customise contents (modify, select, enrich, translate) according to the goal of the activity, the target audience, etc.
- **Live collaboration (during activities):** During the co-design activities, the resources of the toolkit can be used in different ways by the facilitator(s) and the participants: Ingredient Cards and Reflection Questions can be used to stimulate discussion and raise awareness of necessary “ingredients” and related constraints; Canvases can support targeted collaborative tasks.
- **Consolidation and tracking (after activities):** After the collaborative activity, the SIP board can be used to take notes on the selection of ingredients that will describe the SIP. This can be done through a pen-and-paper approach (the SIP board is paper-based) or in a digital form.

The Toolkit resources are made available to SMART ERA project partners in a dedicated folder in the shared project repository. Resources will also be accessible from within the

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digital version of the Toolkit currently under development in task T3.2. After the resources are validated in the six project use cases, the SIP Co-Design Toolkit will be made publicly available.

To help Community Activators and Pilot Orchestrators understand how the Toolkit can be used in practice, illustrated use scenarios have been prepared (these are reported in Annex F of this deliverable). A video presentation explaining the scenarios has also been circulated. A hands-on training session was organised to familiarise users with the physical version of the materials in conjunction with a plenary consortium meeting (Milano, 3rd December 2024). Annex E reports how this training and validation activity was organised.

4.4. SIP Board

Figure 10 displays the base layout for the SIP Board. The board serves as a reference point that shows the progress of the collaborative activity of each case study: the hexagons of the board represent the different categories that should be considered to define a SIP (e.g. people, legal aspects, digital applications, infrastructures, incentives, etc., as described in Chapter 3).

Figure 10. Base layout for the SIP Board

The board can be printed on a large sheet of paper (for example, in A0 size) to create a physical tool supporting individual and group discussions around SIP ingredients. A digital version of the SIP Board is also under development within Task 3.2, as described in Chapter 5.

Stakeholders can progressively record the identified SIP ingredients on the board as they emerge during the various co-design activities (Figure 11, left). Coloured hexagon sticky

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notes (reflecting the colour code of the ingredient categories) representing ingredients can be used to make the physical interaction more intuitive and enjoyable (Figure 11, right).

Figure 11. Sample usage of the SIP Board (left) and example of hexagon-shaped sticky note

Alternative graphical layouts have been experimented with for the design of the SIP Board to additionally pace the identification of the ingredients according to the different phases of the SIP co-creation process (e.g. phase 1: Discover and define the rural challenge, phase 2: Engage and motivate stakeholders, phase 3: Develop and deliver the solution). For the sake of completeness, Annex G reports the alternative layouts that were generated for the SIP Board. The possibility of offering users alternative layouts for the board will be further considered for the implementation of the digital version of the SIP Co-design Toolkit (Task 3.2).

4.5. Ingredients kit

The Ingredients Kit comprises physical cards (and their digital version) that provide information and stimuli on SIP ingredients. These materials can be used to facilitate presentations, brainstorming sessions, workshops, or preparation work by community activators and pilot orchestrators.

4.5.1. Ingredient cards

Each category of ingredients (e.g. “People”, “Digital applications”, “Legal aspects”,...) has an associated set of cards. A presentation card offers a general presentation of the category (Figure 12, left). Other cards describe concrete examples of ingredients of that category that can be used in the SIP and for which purpose (e.g. "local hero", "drones",...) (Figure 12, right). Ingredient cards are aimed at enhancing awareness of opportunities and constraints related to ingredients.

The graphical layout of the Ingredient cards has been optimised for printing on A5-size paper for easy manipulation during brainstorming sessions.

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Figure 12. An example of a presentation card for a category of ingredients (left) and an example of an ingredient card (right)

Figure 13. Overview of the Ingredient cards created for the first version of the SIP Co-design Toolkit

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Overall, 80 ingredients cards were created for the first version of the SIP Co-design Toolkit released at M12 of the project development (Figure 13). This set will be integrated as the SMART ERA project progresses, with material elaborated on other tasks. For example, cards illustrating examples of methods for territorial assessment (from Task 2.1) will be added to the "Smartness assessment" category, and cards illustrating examples of business models (from Task 3.4) will be added to the "Economic enablers" category.

4.5.2. Reflection questions

Reflection Questions contain general questions that help stakeholders understand why the different categories of ingredients are essential and the dependencies between them. Figure 14 shows an example of Reflection Questions prepared to stimulate thinking about the various stakeholders involved in a SIP co-design and deployment.

Reflection Questions can be used in conjunction with ingredient cards or separately. When printed out, A4 size paper can be used.

PEOPLE REFLECTION QUESTIONS	
<p>Understanding the community and its needs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who are the key stakeholders directly affected by the issue we aim to address? Which individuals or groups have valuable insights or firsthand knowledge of the local challenges? Are there any local leaders (hero), respected figures, or community organizations whose support is essential for community involvement? 	<p>Commitment, collaboration and communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How will we ensure ongoing commitment from actors who may have other responsibilities or limited resources? What communication strategies or platforms can support effective, inclusive engagement? Are there any prior relationships, partnerships, or conflicts between these actors that might influence the process?
<p>Roles and contributions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What specific skills, knowledge, or resources are needed for the innovation process? 	<p>Sustainability and long-term impact</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which actors are likely to remain involved after the initial phases of the innovation process, ensuring continuity and long-term impact? Are there local institutions or organizations that can support or maintain the innovation beyond its initial implementation? How can we prepare local actors to eventually take ownership of the innovation process?
<p>Representation and diversity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are we ensuring representation from diverse groups (e.g., age, gender, occupation) to capture a range of perspectives? Have we included voices from marginalized or less visible groups who might be impacted by the innovation? 	

Figure 14. Reflection Questions for the "People" category of ingredients

4.6. Canvases

Canvases are visual templates that can be used to support collaborative discussions on specific aspects of SIPs. They can be used in conjunction with Cards or separately.

Canvases are, for example, available to guide the stakeholders' mapping in the initial stages of problem definition (as illustrated in the scenario described in Annex F.1) or to stimulate reflection on the possible uses of digital ingredients to solve rural challenges (as illustrated

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in the scenario described in Annex F.2). Figure 15 shows one sheet of the Digital Enablers canvas that can be used in the latter scenario. This canvas was obtained from an adaptation of existing resources of the SEROI+ method developed in the previous ERUDITE project¹⁵.

Digital enablers
What can be digitalized in rural areas? How digitalization can support territorial challenges?"

UNDERSTAND DEFINE

Reflect on the challenge of your area and identify one or more digital services that seems very promising to your pilot

What can this chosen digital service bring to your pilot? (value)

Why has the chosen solution not yet been implemented in your pilot?

Which barriers could you foresee for its implementation and deployment?

Write a use scenario in which the solution demonstrates its value for the rural development

Please name at least 3 potential beneficial effects of the chosen digital solution and scenario use in your pilot.

SMART ERA

Figure 15. A sheet of the Digital Enablers canvas. (adapted from the SEROI+ method)

Figure 16 illustrates how the Digital Enablers canvas was used in an early validation test of the resources under development for the SIP Co-design Toolkit that was organised during the SMART ERA plenary meeting in Mallorca (June 2024) and is further described in Annex E. In this case, the canvas was used in its printed form (on A3 size paper) to facilitate face-to-face interactions.

Figure 16. Digital Enablers canvas used during a collaborative workshop in Sòller (Mallorca)

¹⁵ <https://seroi.plus/about/> (last accessed on the 14th of November 2024).

4.7. Other methodological resources for capacity building

As explained in Section 4.3, the SIP Co-design Toolkit is not a general framework for co-design but rather a bespoke resource for facilitating the creation of rural innovation solutions centred around the pivotal SIP concept. Nonetheless, in addition to the resources described in the previous sections (SIP Board, Cards, Reflection Questions, Canvases), the SIP Co-design Toolkit includes other methodological resources that may help SMART ERA stakeholders build (or strengthen) capacity in the organisation of initial context analysis activities or co-design workshops.

The following resources were made available to case study partners in the early phases of project development to support the initial exploratory activities of pilot areas (now reported in deliverable D5.1):

- A guided list of methods to facilitate the needs and gaps analysis, with suggested steps to perform,
- Guidelines for initial problem definition, with a suggested template for problem description (provided by Task 5.1),
- Guidelines for the identification and analysis of stakeholders, with a suggested template for their description (provided by Task 5.1),
- Template tables for data sources mapping and analysis (provided in conjunction with Task 5.1).

New resources for capacity building in co-design will be progressively added to the Toolkit as they are prepared for or collected during the case study activities, to be readily available when follower regions test the SMART ERA SIP-based approach to innovation. Materials resulting from other European projects related to the development of rural areas (e.g., Smart Villages, Smart Communities, Nevermore, ...) will be reused whenever possible.

5. Towards a hybrid (physical and digital) co-design toolkit

As part of the research work in Task 3.2, to better engage stakeholders and at the same time provide a real-time monitoring during the co-design activities, we designed and started developing a digital counterpart of the toolkit.

We started with a systematic analysis of existing gameful co-design toolkits. Then, we distilled some principles to develop the digital component.

This chapter reports the ongoing activities carried out in Task 3.2. Further details and advancements will be described in deliverable D3.2 at M24.

5.1. Literature review

To analyse the gameful digital tools in a systematic manner, we conducted a search in two databases: Association for Information Systems (AIS) eLibrary (AISeL), and Scopus. We used the query “(TITLE-ABS-KEY (codesign) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (codesign) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (co-participation) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (coparticipation) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (participatory AND design) AND TITLE-ABSKEY (gam*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (rural) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (community) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (collective AND actions))”.

The search yielded 173 results from the AISeL database and 355 from the Scopus database, with a total of 528 hits. Subsequently, a snowballing technique was applied, identifying additional 15 potential hits by analysing the references of the initially retrieved documents. This process resulted in a total of 543 documents being selected for title and abstract screening. We defined the following inclusion criteria: (1) the study should report the use of game strategies (digital and analogic), in (2) co-design meetings (3) directly involving stakeholders to promote the (4) co-design, co-production, and co-delivery of interventions or collective actions for (5) communities or rural areas.

After the title-abstract screening procedure, 490 papers were excluded following the inclusion/exclusion criteria. After the full-text review of the remaining 53 publications, 31 articles were excluded because they did not meet the inclusion criteria or did not contain relevant information. In total, 22 studies were eligible for the review.

5.1.1. Preliminary results

The deadline for the literature review is due in M24 (D3.2), however some preliminary results have already emerged. The first thing that is possible to notice from our analysis, is that the totality of the tools identified in the review are domain-specific, and designed for particular contexts or challenges. This specificity restricts their transferability and adaptability to broader or diverse co-design scenarios, particularly those targeting rural communities with unique needs and resource constraints. Moreover, none of them has implemented *phygital* methodologies, i.e. methodologies combining the strengths of analog systems with those of digital systems. Within the searched publications, 7 studies included a wide variety of

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stakeholders (citizens, decision makers, farmers, researchers), providing a background for multi-stakeholder engagement.

Interestingly, analyzing the scientific reliability of the studies, 62.5% of them proved to be below average, reporting an unclear number of participants, unclear methodology, and a poor data collection and analysis methodologies. Overall, from this analysis we can state that there is no general standardized co-design procedure; hence, it is difficult to determine their effectiveness, impact, and engagement based on data reported.

This review reveals that there is a great opportunity to propose a (data-driven) standard procedure for gameful co-design of interventions in rural areas, and to improve the methods of research in the field.

5.2. Digital tool

Building from these preliminary results, we started working on a SIP digital gameful co-design tool as an extension of the analogue SIP Co-design Toolkit presented in the previous chapters. We stated 7 key requirements:

- **Adaptive participation modes.** To accommodate different user preferences and contexts, the designed tool should allow flexibility in its application as a fully physical, fully digital, or hybrid system.
- **Data transfer.** Recognizing the need for continuity between physical and digital activities, the tool should include streamlined mechanisms for transferring data from physical to digital formats.
- **Structured collaboration management.** To support large-scale and collaborative co-design projects, the tool should implement a user privilege system. This feature should allow administrators to assign specific access levels, enabling designated “pilot orchestrators” to access data, compare project outcomes, and disseminate results across multiple projects. By facilitating information sharing, the privilege system supports cross-project learning and transparency.
- **Simultaneous multi-project capability.** The tool’s architecture is designed to accommodate multiple projects, or “pilots”, concurrently. This multi-project functionality will allow stakeholders to manage and compare different interventions within the same interface promoting efficiency and enabling a comprehensive view of various initiatives.
- **Universal applicability.** To extend the tool’s applicability across different types of co-design initiatives, we have adopted a domain-agnostic approach. This feature makes the tool easily adaptable to various contexts, from rural planning to urban design or environmental sustainability interventions. The tool’s modular design should allow for rapid customization, making it suitable for a wide range of co-design applications without requiring significant reconfiguration.
- **Engagement through visual feedback.** Incorporating gamified elements, the tool visualizes progress through icons that provide a clear, accessible indication of advancement. Unlike raw quantitative metrics that vary widely across projects (such as participant numbers), these icons offer a standardized representation of project milestones, enhancing user motivation and engagement. This gamified approach will

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encourage stakeholders by clearly showcasing the project’s journey and achievements.

- **Guided process framework.** The tool incorporates the Double Diamond model, a widely accepted design methodology that organizes the co-design process into four stages: Discover and Define within the “problem definition” phase, and Develop and Deliver within the “solution definition” phase. This procedural framework will guide users through structured phases, ensuring a comprehensive approach to problem-solving and innovation.

Although the deadline for the gameful co-design digital tool is set at M24 (D3.2), a first prototype version, including a subset of functionalities, has already been developed to take advantage of early feedback from project partners. The digital tool totally incorporates the functionalities and structure of the analogue one, and at the same time adds elements of visualization and gamification.

Figure 17 shows the SIP board view, along with some elements related to the status of SIP co-design, including the health of the co-design process, instances considered, and number of sessions. The number of instances shows users how many ingredient instances were evaluated in total within the project, providing an idea of how many actors and elements were identified for the creation of a SIP. The number of work sessions reflects how often stakeholders were involved, providing a sort of thermometer of the level of engagement of the stakeholder network. The health of the pilot/SIP is a measure that provides insight into how well the process is going, mixing data derived from the number and variety of stakeholders, number of working sessions, number of ingredients analysed and instances created, and how often the facilitator interacts with the digital tool.

Figure 17. Board view in the digital tool

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Figure 18 shows the inspection of various elements within an ingredient category, and the display of ingredient cards.

Figure 18. Instances within an ingredient category, in this case “People”, and display of ingredient cards

Figure 19 depicts the pilot view. In this board, the tool presents the same co-design status elements (number of instances, number of sessions and SIP health), along with a timer. The timer shows two pieces of information: it indicates how long it has been (in days) since the facilitator last updated and interacted with the digital tool and how much time remains (in the form of an arc timer) before losing the next streak badge.

Figure 19. Pilot view with two different examples of use, dairy supply and forestry management

Conclusions

The activities carried out within Task 3.1 during the first year of SMART ERA project development had the important objective of defining an **operative definition for the concept of Smart Innovation Packages for rural development**. Through a series of collaborative activities with Community Activators, Pilot Orchestrators as well as academic and technical partners with complementary backgrounds and skills, specific requirements were distilled on what constitutes SIPs and how they can be designed, described and reused.

It clearly emerged that a SIP may be created in an incremental way, possibly during long-term iterative cycles, with complementary subparts, with adaptations needed for replicability. This implies that **there is no one rigid SIP co-design process** that may fit all case studies. It is however possible to offer to rural communities inspiration and guidance for the composition of suites of technological and non-technological ingredients that solve their rural challenges. A **bespoke SIP Co-design Toolkit** has been developed for this purpose.

- The co-design toolkit has been designed to guarantee **flexibility of use** to accommodate different design journeys and paces.
- The toolkit **does not have the ambition to be exhaustive**, i.e. to include all possible examples of ingredients. It aims, instead, at offering **a methodology to categorise and exemplify ingredients** that toolkit users can extend with their own ideas as necessary.
- The toolkit will be a **living resource** that will be iteratively refined and integrated with material developed in other SMART ERA Work Packages during the course of the project.

During the second year of project development, the SIP Co-design Toolkit will be used by the six SMART ERA case studies to collaboratively design their Smart Innovation Package. Digital functionalities complementing the SIP Co-design Toolkit will be consolidated within Task 3.2.

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Annex A – Intuitive examples of SIPs

This Annex includes some intuitive examples of bundles of technological and non-technological ingredients that can be used in synergy to solve challenges impacting on rural development. These examples were used during different presentations and collaborative reflection activities within T3.1 to brainstorm on the SIP concept and related co-design processes.

A.1 SIP for a cooperative of farmers

This example was inspired by a real-use scenario of a cooperative of farmers¹⁶ where the intent was to join farmers' forces to rent expensive equipment and use it in turns.

Figure 20. Sample SIP for a cooperative of farmers

A.2 SIP for an on-demand mobility service

This example was inspired by a real scenario of an on-demand mobility service created for a tourist destination in Northern Italy¹⁷.

¹⁶ <https://www.ruminantia.it/macchinari-agricoli-in-condivisione-lesperienza-della-coop-agr-di-marene/> (last accessed on the 11th of November 2024).

¹⁷ <https://www.gardatrentino.it/it/organizza/trasporti-mobilita/Bus-and-Go> (last accessed on the 23rd of November 2024).

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Figure 21. Sample SIP for an on-demand mobility service

A.3 SIP for a school of shepherds

This example was inspired by two distinct projects investigating the challenge of training young people living in remote rural areas as shepherds¹⁸.

Figure 22. Sample SIP for a school of shepherds

¹⁸ <https://www.reterurale.it/giovanipastori> and <https://www.innovazione sociale.org/index.php/1409-arriva-il-pastore-4-0-in-calabria-l-antico-mestiere-diventa-smart-per-attrarre-i-giovani-e-rilanciare-le-aree-montane>. (last accessed on 23 November 2024).

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A.4 SIP for the development of local crops

This example was inspired by two projects investigating the challenge of sustaining the cultivation of local cereals¹⁹.

Figure 23. Sample SIP for the development of local crops

¹⁹ <https://www.unimontagna.it/progetti/buone-pratiche-per-la-coltivazione-e-la-trasformazione-di-cereali-alpini-e-piante-officinali-ceralp/> and <https://www.pulsesincrease.eu/experiment> (Increase European project) (last accessed on the 23rd of November 2024)

Annex B – Workshop on innovation processes in rural areas

Workshop - Participatory processes in the pilot territories (learning together from past experiences in (co)designing innovation services in rural areas)
Trento, 17th of January 2024

B.1 Objective and structure of the workshop

One week before the SMART ERA project kick-off meeting (held on the 17-18 January 2024 in Trento, Italy), Community Activators were asked to reflect (with the help of Pilot Orchestrators) on previous experiences organised in their rural territory for the collaborative creation of innovation. To facilitate this homework, a template schema for slides (jointly developed by FBK, POLI and ANYSOL) was circulated in advance to guide their reflection on the type of service that was created (Figure 24), on the creation process that was followed (Figure 25), and on the positive vs. challenging aspects that were encountered (Figure 26).

<p>Exercise 1: Briefly describe a previous experience of innovation</p> <p>Think back to previous initiatives in your territory aimed at the creation of new innovative services</p> <p>If available, concentrate on experiences that involved a collaboration between different stakeholders</p> <p>Experiences that are related to rural issues are particularly interesting</p> <p>Select one experience that you believe is particularly interesting</p> <p>Briefly describe the service that was created following the provided template table, as in the examples below.</p> <p>➔ Remember that the goal is to start understanding together how innovation processes are initiated and unfold</p>	<p>P1 PREVIOUS EXPERIENCE</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Initiative / Service name</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Goal of the service</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Description</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How the initiative was born? E.g., requested by citizens / data-driven need identification / project opportunity / other... How the service was structured / how did it work? </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Involved stakeholders</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What categories How many How the stakeholders were selected and engaged </td> </tr> </table>	Initiative / Service name		Goal of the service		Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How the initiative was born? E.g., requested by citizens / data-driven need identification / project opportunity / other... How the service was structured / how did it work? 	Involved stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What categories How many How the stakeholders were selected and engaged
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Goal of the service									
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Involved stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What categories How many How the stakeholders were selected and engaged 								

Figure 24. Exercise 1 for Workshop 1 in Trento

<p>Exercise 2: Recall the executed collaborative process</p> <p>Try to list the main steps you had to perform to create that service/initiative</p> <p>Phases and steps often correspond to problems to solve or information to gather before the service creation progresses. Think back to the difficulties you had to face and the data you had to collect.</p> <p>Adapt and fill the procedural steps as shown in the following template.</p>	<p>WHAT WORKED WELL / WHAT WAS DIFFICULT</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Successes / best practices</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What worked particularly well? What would you suggest to do to other rural areas? </td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Main difficulties /</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which are the most difficult activities? What resources useful for the process were missing? </td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	Successes / best practices		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What worked particularly well? What would you suggest to do to other rural areas? 		Main difficulties /		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which are the most difficult activities? What resources useful for the process were missing? 	
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Main difficulties /									
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which are the most difficult activities? What resources useful for the process were missing? 									

Figure 25. Exercise 2 for Workshop 1 in Trento

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<p>Exercise 3: Reflect on how the experience went</p> <p>Are there best practices that you normally apply that facilitate the service creation process?</p> <p>Which are the difficulties that you encountered in participatory processes?</p> <p>What type of resources you feel are currently missing?</p>	<p>HOW THE SERVICE CREATION PROCESS UNFOLDED</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>01</td> <td>Initial idea envisioning</td> <td>05</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>02</td> <td></td> <td>06</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>03</td> <td></td> <td>07</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>04</td> <td></td> <td>08</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	01	Initial idea envisioning	05		02		06		03		07		04		08	
01	Initial idea envisioning	05															
02		06															
03		07															
04		08															

Figure 26. Exercise 3 for Workshop 1 in Trento

Following the provided template, partners responsible for each of the six pilots produced a story narrating an already implemented experience of rural innovation, as shown in Figure 27.

HOW THE SERVICE CREATION PROCESS UNFOLDED			
01	Initial idea envisioning by the Agricultural Cooperative of Sóller sought an external skilled coordinator activities in Sóller that could bring together rural community and tourists/interest	09	Adaptation of the service to seasonal and regional needs
02	First contact The president of the cooperativa MesCultura, seeking their services	10	Feedback of the peasants and producers They have helped us to improve the visits and the ideas to transmit to visitors.
03	Formal collaboration agreement established between Cooperativa MesCultura, wherein MesCultura Centre Capvespre and provides s	11	The first big step “EDUCTUR” (EU project) to approach the primary sector to tourists
04	Formulating a service idea Collection and evaluation of ideas activities and stakeholders	12	Feedback We had a lot of Feedback from -the Consortium “ Serra de Tramuntana” -the Balearic Government; -The Town Hall from the Tourism and economic promotion department
		13	Improvements Creation and execution of two different exhibitions to inform about local agriculture and products

Figure 27. A previous service creation process for rural development that was implemented in Sóller (Mallorca)

On the 17th of January 2024, the two-hour workshop then unfolded into three main stages:

- a brief introduction (10 minutes) by a researcher of FBK explained the aim of the workshop;
- during the central part of the workshop, a representative of each pilot area, in turn, briefly presented one previous experience of (participatory) creation of services in their territory (approximately 15-20 minutes). After each presentation, comments, reflections, and clarification questions were interactively discussed with the audience, facilitated by partners FBK, POLIEDRA and ANYSOL.

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- In the last 10 minutes of the workshop, a researcher by FBK briefly wrapped up the activities by explaining how the collected information would be elaborated by identifying commonalities and distinguishing aspects of the 6 pilot areas.

All project members participating in the kick-off meeting participated in the workshop (50 participants).

B.2 Results

Each innovation story narrated during the workshop was analysed to factor out information about 1) how the process was initiated, 2) how the stakeholders' network was engaged, 3) what methods were used for context analysis, 4) how the creation and development process unfolded, 5) implementation aspects, 6) barriers, 7) sustainability issues and 8) monitoring practices. Figure 28 shows, for example, some relevant facts extracted from the innovation story reported by +CULTURA for the Sóller/Mallorca pilot.

Figure 28. Analysis of one of the innovation stories emerged from the workshop

The facts distilled for the six pilots were then organised in a summary board offering a comparative analysis clustered according to the eight selected research dimensions listed above (Figure 29). A numeric and colour code was assigned to each pilot to facilitate the organisation of contents and the following analysis.

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Figure 29. Comparative analysis of significant facts in innovation stories emerged from the workshop

For each research dimension, the comparative analysis investigated similarities and the variety of approaches. Figure 30 shows a detail of recurrent concepts emerging for the development approach adopted in the different pilots (e.g. "replicability" for pilot 1-Val di Sole, 3-Northern Ostrobothnia and 4-East Herzegovina), as well as the different context-dependent nuances (e.g. "repeating the process for new municipalities" for pilot 3-Northern Ostrobothnia vs. "repeating the process for new products" for pilot 4-East Herzegovina).

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Figure 30. Detail of recurrent concepts.

B.3 Discussion

The outputs of the first workshop on participatory processes in the pilot territories served a double goal:

- 1) preparing the ground for the second workshop reflecting on what a SIP is (described in Annex C), thanks to the creation and sharing of a set of varied rural innovation stories stemming from different territorial contexts, to be used as food for thoughts to stimulate the discussion on which are the essential ingredients of a Smart Innovation Package;
- 2) helping to distil relevant features of successful innovation processes for rural development that were translated into requirements for SIPs' co-design processes.

Regarding the second point, the following relevant features emerged from the comparative analysis performed over the input collected before and during the workshop.

Process initiation

Different governance models were observed in the narrated rural innovation stories. Some initiatives were initiated with a **bottom-up approach** based on the ideas of local activists. A **middle-out approach** was instead reported for a local cooperative that interpreted the needs of local producers. In other cases, a **top-down approach** was sparked by public administrations in compliance with national policy decisions; this political advocacy then favoured commitment to innovation by local administrations in a context with hierarchical structures of public bodies. In general, there may be different degrees of involvement in civil society (e.g., only consultation, participation in decision-making or service delivery, volunteering,...). This variety of governance models for the co-production of rural innovation calls for a **flexible concept of SIP in terms of ideation, management and ownership**.

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Stakeholders network engagement

Motivation of participants is essential. There must be effective ways to activate it and sustain it in time. Indeed, different stakeholders may participate at various stages of the process. Sometimes, a long-term engagement may be required, which is difficult to obtain: in this case, engagement could be facilitated by resorting to **consolidated networks**. Synergies between public bodies, civil society, companies and academia have the potential to boost innovation processes. The involvement of **young, motivated people** can boost processes. Identifying one stakeholder who can play the role of a "**local hero**" or community activator is fundamental to keeping things going.

Nonetheless, external **expert consultation** may be needed to bootstrap initiatives. Indeed, local rural areas may first need help to **build capacity** for implementing innovation (e.g., by providing them with know-how, examples, clear benefits, skilled workforce, data resources, etc.). In-person public events may be vital in engaging the community, listening to local population needs and eliciting bottom-up ideas. However, the process must be flexible and adapt to different territorial contexts that may have their own specific constraints, like, for example, difficulties in getting in contact with local producers due to the digital gap (e.g., no email access) or problems in reaching an agreement with them.

The network of stakeholders is a living body that might need extension and modification to **adapt the group of involved people** over time according to the evolving project needs.

Context analysis

Data are a valuable asset for better understanding the context, identifying problems and areas best suited for intervention, and evaluating results. Complementary methodologies for territorial assessment have been reported by the pilots in previous experiences, like the usage of methodologies that combine socio-economic and environmental return on investment assessment (e.g., SEROI+) and tools that evaluate digital maturity and support decision-making for future digital transformation strategies (e.g. Smartness assessment method).

Development approach

It may take a long time to reach the end of the service creation process. For this reason, an **incremental approach** to service creation is often adopted (e.g., with geographical coverage enlarged with small steps or new contents created in iterative cycles). **Replicating the process**, with lessons learned, in a new municipality or for a new product is also an applied strategy. Achieving **early success stories** helps the incremental approach, favours replicability, helps find funding and helps return results to stakeholders.

Project implementation

The solution to a rural challenge may actually be a bundle of services (e.g., health education, proximity services, telemedicine services). Therefore, **implementation complementarity with other actions** may be required.

Skilled personnel and physical infrastructures may be fundamental ingredients for the implementation of the new services.

The implementation of the service might need to ensure the **adaptability of the service over time** to adapt to changing seasons, regional needs or different visitors' needs (this is typical, for example, for innovation related to sectors strongly affected by seasonality, like agriculture and tourism).

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Sustainability

Law or policy changes may significantly facilitate or speed up the process, although awareness campaigns to improve local public administrations' understanding of the potential benefits of certain types of innovations may be required.

Financial resources are a fundamental ingredient.

Continuity of action sometimes comes from the complementarity of projects stemming from different funding opportunities. Creating **business models** is critical to address sustainability concretely.

Monitoring

There is a need for **monitoring during the process** and implementation of **periodic evaluation and improvement** to take into account feedback emerging from the stakeholders.

Annex C – Workshop on innovation ingredients

Workshop - What will the SMART ERA Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs) be? Trento, 17th of January 2024

C.1 Objectives and structure of the workshop

Right at the beginning of the SMART ERA project development, all consortium partners were involved in a joint discussion to create a shared understanding of the factors that enter into play in building solutions to rural innovation challenges. To this aim, a two-hour workshop was organised in conjunction with the SMART ERA project kick-off meeting (held on the 17-18 January 2024 in Trento, Italy) to (i) discuss concrete examples of "ingredients" that function as facilitators or enablers for the creation and deployment of innovative services in rural areas, (ii) understand the different types of ingredients, and (iii) the phases where they enter into play. Results from the Workshop described in Annex B provided inspiration, as several examples of very different rural innovation processes had been shared immediately before this second workshop.

The workshop unfolded into three main phases:

- A brief introduction (15 minutes) by a researcher of FBK explained the workshop's aim and structure.
- During the first hour, partners were split into 3 smaller groups, each moderated by representatives of FBK, POLI, and ANYSOL. An additional group was created for online participants, moderated by FBK. Each in-presence group contained representatives of at least two pilots (P1 Trentino + P4 Trebinje; P2 Tramuntana/Soller + P6 Devetaki Plateau; P3 Northern Ostrobothnia + P5 Šmarje) and a mix of other project partners. Participants in each group worked at generating examples of “ingredients” that are useful during the (participatory) creation and deployment of innovation services in rural areas. Moderators made it clear that the aim of the workshop was not to identify the exact ingredients that will be required by the 6 pilots (as this will be done starting from M13 in Task 3.3 on the co-design of SIPs) but to understand what different categories of ingredients exist, more in general. Participants were encouraged to describe their ideas of “ingredients” following a template card printed on paper (Figure 31.a). For each example, a post-it note with the name of the “ingredient” was attached to a summary poster available on the table (Figure 31.b).
- During the remaining 45 minutes, in a plenary session, the moderator of each group (from FBK, POLI and ANYSOL) briefly reported the discussion results by illustrating the summary poster. It was highlighted that this material would be used in the following weeks to identify different categories/types of “ingredients” that emerged

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from the group work and what it means to bundle different “ingredients” together to create a SIP.

All project members participating in the SMART ERA kick-off meeting participated in the workshop (50 participants).

Figure 31. Stimulus materials provided to support the discussion. (a) On the left, the template to describe sample ingredients, and (b) on the right, the poster to organise ideas

C.2 Results

The workshop generated a rich amount of content: overall, 91 sample ingredients were mentioned either in the "ingredient cards" (Figure 32), post-its on summary posters, input collected during the online workgroup, or post-workshop email contributions.

Figure 32. Examples of ingredient cards filled out by participants during the workshop.

All the contents were systematically transcribed into an Excel file, which recorded an evocative name for the ingredient, the group work in which the ingredient was mentioned, its general type (data / policy / best practice / software / hardware / equipment / goods / human expert / agreement / other), the co-production phase in which it was considered

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useful, how it was described (in written text or verbally), the problem it was mentioned to solve. To facilitate the analysis of ingredients that emerged in different workgroups, a Mural board was prepared with all the names of the ingredients, as illustrated in Figure 33, where different colours identify input from various groups at a glance.

Figure 33. Mural board collecting all the ingredients that emerged from group work during the workshop

An affinity diagram was then created to aggregate similar ingredients into categories and subcategories. The diagram was enriched with a further 46 sample ingredients extracted from the analysis of the rural innovation stories narrated in the first workshop on participatory processes described in Annex B. The organisation of the affinity diagram was discussed and refined by three FBK researchers, and reflections during this phase led to the emergence of 20 additional ingredients.

The final categorization included 157 examples of ingredients, grouped into ten main categories:

- Data and knowledge on context
- Software
- Best practices
- Communication and training
- Incentives
- Financial and economic enablers
- Infrastructure

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- Equipment
- Political/legal aspects
- People

Figure 34 illustrates how each category was divided into meaningful subcategories.

C1	DATA AND KNOWLEDGE ON CONTEXT	C5	INCENTIVES
C1.1	Digital data	C5.1	Tangible incentives / benefits
C1.2	Non digital data / knowledge / ideas / opinions	C5.2	Incentivisation strategies
C1.2.1	Indigenous knowledge	C5.3	Digitally supported incentives
C1.3	Expert analysis	C6	FINANCIAL & ECONOMIC ENABLERS
C1.4	Opportunities / key features of the territory	C6.1	Funding
C1.5	Standards for digital data	C6.2	Market context
C1.6	Training for data interpretation	C6.3	Business models
C2	SOFTWARE	C7	INFRASTRUCTURE
C2.1	Software for data analysis / modeling / decision making	C7.1	Digital infrastructures
C2.2	Software to support collaboration and participation	C7.2	Physical infrastructures
C2.3	Software for service implementation (applications)	C7.2.1	Spaces
C3	BEST PRACTICES	C7.2.2	Roads/Trails
C3.1	Best practices for community creation & engagement	C7.2.3	Other
C3.2	Best practices for management	C8	EQUIPMENT
C3.3	Best practices for inclusion	C8.1	Physical equipment
C3.4	Best practices for collaboration	C8.2	Digital equipment
C3.5	Best practices of knowledge elicitation	C8.3	Physical objects
C3.6	Best practices for service creation	C9	POLITICAL / LEGAL ASPECTS
C3.7	Best practices for monitoring & evaluation	C9.1	Political enablers
C4	COMMUNICATION AND TRAINING	C9.2	Strategies for exchange and replication
C4.1	Communication & awareness rising	C9.3	Formal agreements
C4.2	Training and capacity building	C9.4	Legal documents
C4.3	Communication on products / new services	C10	PEOPLE
		C10.1	Human experts / Facilitators
		C10.2	Participants

Figure 34. Initial grouping of "ingredients" into 10 categories and 50 subcategories, as emerged from the second workshop

C.3 Discussion

The mix of multidisciplinary backgrounds and previous experiences of participants in each workgroup let emerge different perspectives and points of view that clearly validate the SMART ERA vision that community-led territorial development requires the creation of an ecosystem made up of "ingredients" that go well beyond the practicalities of service delivery (like materials, infrastructures, or human operators).

The workshop results laid the basis for further research towards a possible categorization of ingredient types (described in Chapter 3) as an important tool to help rural communities build capacity in performing co-production processes. Several lessons learned and requirements were also distilled:

- Ingredients can be categorised in alternative ways. For example, strategies for community engagement can be considered as belonging to a separate category of

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"Best practices", as was done during the analysis of workshop results (Figure 34), or they can be considered as essential ingredients to better frame the "People" category.

- SMART ERA does not aim to create an exhaustive catalogue of ingredients for rural innovation, as this would be an encyclopaedic task whose effort goes beyond the project's scope.
- Concrete examples of ingredients of different categories, proposed by experts or coming from the experience of other territories, are of inspiration for rural communities committed to innovation.
- Stakeholders in rural areas have yet to discover ingredients related to digital technologies (digital data, software applications, bespoke hardware devices) and their related opportunities.
- There exist tasks in the SMART ERA workplan that can provide fruitful input for the creation of reusable SIP ingredients like business models to make rural innovations sustainable (Task 3.4), updated knowledge on rural policies (WP6), methodologies to assess the local context before and after the interventions (Task 2.1), data dashboards to support decision making (Task 4.2).

Annex D – Workshop on digital ingredients

Workshop: What can be digitised in rural areas? How can digitalization support territorial challenges?

Soller, 6th of June 2024

D.1 Objectives and structure of the workshop

During the second plenary consortium meeting of the SMART ERA project, held in Soller (Mallorca) on the 6-7 June 2024, a workshop was organised with multiple objectives in order to:

- deepen the consortium's shared awareness about technological / digital solutions that may contribute to rural development;
- brainstorm on the potential relevance of digital ingredients for the six SMART ERA case studies;
- collect ideas to extend the presented draft list of digital enablers with other solutions specific for case studies' needs;
- reflect on type of solutions with the higher replication/up-taking possibilities for rural areas in Europe;
- reflect on the limits and constraints of using certain technologies in some rural contexts;
- validate with Community Activators and Pilot Orchestrators preliminary concepts of the SIP Co-design Toolkit that was under development, i.e. the usage of Cards to stimulate reflection through illustrated examples of digital ingredients and the usage of Canvases to guide the discussion.

The workshop involved the 43 participants to the meeting and unfolded into the following phases:

- Right before the beginning of the workshop, in a plenary session all participants were exposed to the presentation by technical partners contributing to WP4 of digital solutions already available and tested in previous projects for the implementation of innovation in rural and non-rural areas.
- Still in a plenary session, a researcher from UL introduced the workshop objectives and a researcher from FBK offered a presentation of a set of ingredient Cards describing potential digital enablers for rural innovation (20 min.)

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- Participants then divided in three rooms (plus one online group for partners participating from remote). Each room hosted representatives from two case studies, split in two tables. Technical partners distributed across the various tables, in order to have mixed background and skills in each group. (The setting is illustrated in previous Figure 16 in section 4.6). Facilitators from UL, FBK and POLI supported the team work.
- Each group was asked to select a set of digital solutions that seem particularly relevant to the challenges of their territory, from the list presented in the digital Cards (10 mins.)
- Pilots were then invited to agree upon one most promising digital solution and potential use scenario and to work on it by following the proposed Canvas (40 min).
- At the end of the group activity, a plenary session concluded the workshop with a peer review phase, when a representative of each group synthesised what emerged at their table.

Figure 35 illustrates the canvases used to stimulate the activity, which were derived from an adaptation of materials included in the SEROI+ methodology.

The figure displays four canvases used for group discussion during the workshop. Each canvas is a structured form with text prompts and empty boxes for input.

Canvas 1 (Top Left): Titled "Considering what just presented, please name in the box below digital solutions with use scenarios that are relevant for your pilot" and "Add in this box other ideas of digital solutions that are missing from the list". It contains two large empty boxes. Below the boxes, it says: "For the next steps, choose one of the digital solutions above, which you think is particular interesting for your pilot."

Canvas 2 (Top Right): Titled "What can be digitalized in rural areas? How digitalization can support territorial challenges?". It contains four smaller empty boxes. The prompts are: "Identify and name one digital service and its use scenario that seems very promising to your pilot", "What can this chosen digital service and its use scenario bring to your pilot altogether?", "Why has the chosen solution not yet been implemented in your pilot?", and "What is already there (information, knowledge, business models, infrastructures, policy support)? Please, be as specific as possible." It includes a "Support Sheet" button and the SMART ERA logo.

Canvas 3 (Bottom Left): Titled "What can be digitalized in rural areas? How digitalization can support territorial challenges?". It contains six smaller empty boxes. The prompts are: "Who needs to be involved in the development of this service/solution with the use scenario and what is needed?", "What does it do?", "Please name at least 3 beneficial effects of the chosen digital solution and scenario use in your pilot.", "Please, try to think about possible cooperation, local or transnational in regard to your reviewed potential digital solution & use scenarios.", "What are the main needs + personas (you/what the possible user* of the chosen service and scenario use)", "Do we have enough knowledge, technology, resources to create the services?", "Do services have social, economic and environmental value?", and "Do you think users and operators/providers would find services useful, usable and efficient?". It includes a "Support Sheet" button and the SMART ERA logo.

Canvas 4 (Bottom Right): Titled "Digital Services – What WOWS?". It contains a diagram with a dashed line and a solid line, and several empty boxes. The prompts are: "What's there?", "What are your priority goals?", "Which services already exist in your region?", "Which services already exist in your partner regions, also business models?", "What if?", "Perception of user needs + personas (you/what the possible user* of the chosen service and scenario use)", "What are they?", "Do we have enough knowledge, technology, resources to create the services?", "Do services have social, economic and environmental value?", "What works?", and "Do you think users and operators/providers would find services useful, usable and efficient?". It includes the SMART ERA logo.

Figure 35. Canvases used to facilitate group discussion during the workshop

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D.2 Results

Each work group in the workshop generated interesting contents that envisaged how current needs and gaps of the territories are matched by technological solutions. Figure 36 shows sample input that was produced by workshop participants.

Figure 36. Material produced in the workshop group of the East Herzegovina case study

D.3 Discussion

In general, the type of practical activity proposed in the workshop was very well received by Community Activators and Pilot Orchestrators, who showed appreciation for the ingredient Cards and the guidance offered by the Canvases. This represented a preliminary validation of the design concepts of the SIP Co-design Toolkit.

Another valuable outcome of the workshop was the collection of concrete examples of digital/technological ingredients' potential usage. From one side, participants took inspiration from the stimuli that were presented to them by technical partners and researchers. From the other side, they were able to envisage additional digital enablers for their needs. This was used to enrich the categorization of digital ingredients included in the first version of the SIP Co-design Toolkit, as described in Chapter 3.

Annex E – Workshop on SIP Co-design Toolkit training and validation

Hands-on workshop with the analog SIP Co-design Toolkit
Milano, 3rd December 2024

E.1 Objectives and structure of the workshop

During the third plenary consortium meeting of the SMART ERA project, held in Milano (Italy) on the 3-4 December 2024, a workshop was organised with multiple objectives in order to:

- Let all SMART ERA partners (and in particular Community Activators and Pilot Orchestrators) **familiarise with the task of identifying ingredients for a SIP** solving a given rural challenge;
- Let all partners **examine the analog materials of the SIP Co-design Toolkit** in the context of a simulated brainstorming session and **train on the usage of the toolkit** with a hands-on activity implementing a "learning by doing" approach;
- **Collect feedback on the content** (ingredient categorization, cards, reflection questions) included in the first version of the SIP Co-design Toolkit;
- **Observe how the toolkit was received and how it was used.**

The workshop involved all the 48 partners' representatives taking part in the project meeting. During the initial 15 minutes of the workshop, a researcher from FBK briefly recalled who may be the potential users of the SIP Co-Design Toolkit be (facilitators, core work group, and extended groups of local stakeholders) and the flexible ways in which the toolkit can be used (Figure 37).

WHO ARE THE POTENTIAL USERS OF THE TOOLKIT MATERIAL?		FLEXIBLE USE OF THE TOOLKIT		
<p>It depends on your pilot, on the co-design phase, on the skills of involved people</p>	<p>FACILITATORS Persons who operatively organise activities</p>	FACILITATORS / CORE WORK GROUP	CORE WORK GROUP / STAKEHOLDERS GROUP	FACILITATORS / CORE WORK GROUP
	<p>CORE WORK GROUP Pilot Orchestrators and Community Activators, together with a small subset of local stakeholders</p>	PREPARATION (BEFORE ACTIVITIES)	CO-DESIGN WS / COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITY	CONSOLIDATION & TRACKING
	<p>ENLARGED STAKEHOLDERS GROUPS Local stakeholders involved in specific co-design activities</p>	<p>The toolkit supports the facilitator to become aware of the different "ingredients" types that should be considered. The facilitator can use the toolkit to prepare the co-design activities and customize contents (modify, select, enrich) according to the goal of the activity, the target audience, etc.</p>	<p>During the co-design activities, the resources of the toolkit can be used in different ways by the facilitator and the participants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CARDS can be used to stimulate discussion and raise awareness of necessary "ingredients" - CANVASES can support collaborative activities - ... 	<p>After the collaborative activity, the SIP Board can be used to take notes on the selection of ingredients that will describe the SIP. This can be done through a pen-and-paper approach (the SIP board is paper-based) or in a digital form.</p>

Figure 37. Explanations provided to workshop participants during the presentation of the training session

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Participants were then presented with a fictitious (but realistic) scenario of a rural community in need of creating a SIP for a hypothetical on-demand public transportation service, in support of the local community and tourists. Participants were asked to engage in a discussion about the required ingredients to implement the expected SIP.

Participants were then presented with a fictitious (but realistic) scenario of a rural community in need of creating a SIP for a hypothetical on-demand public transportation service, in support of the local community and tourists. Participants were asked to engage in a discussion about the required ingredients to implement the expected SIP.

The 48 participants were divided into three separate groups. Each group was assigned the task of identifying potential ingredients related to three or four different categories: group 1 was expected to reason on digital applications, local knowledge, and financial and economic enablers; group 2 brainstormed on hardware and digital infrastructure, people, incentives and legal aspects; group 3 brainstormed on data, physical infrastructure and equipment, communication and training, and political enablers. Each discussion table was equipped with a canvas to collect ideas and ingredient cards, together with the related how-tos and reflection questions for the considered categories. A researcher from FBK was present in each group to further provide explanations on how to take advantage of the toolkit analog materials to support the identification of ingredients (Figure 38). Ideas were annotated on coloured hexagon-shaped sticky notes.

Figure 38. SMART ERA partners engaging in the training session with the analogue SIP Co-design Toolkit

After 30 minutes of group work, in a final plenary session, representatives of each group were invited to present what ingredients emerged at their table, while attaching the

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completed sticky notes on a common SIP Board hanging in a visible place of the meeting room.

E.2 Results

In only half an hour, each work group was able to quickly initiate the discussion and generate several ideas for ingredients. Overall, 73 sticky notes were added to the SIP Board (Figure 39).

It is important to note that for this training activity the actual information attached to the SIP Board is not of crucial importance, given the fictitious scenario chosen and the fact that this SIP will not be really implemented. Nonetheless, the exercise worked out very well: the complementary expertise of the different participants enabled to elaborate interesting insights for each of the considered ingredient categories and several considerations emerged from the type of generated output, from the suggestions on how to extend the material of the SIP Co-design Toolkit, and from what was observed on the toolkit usage.

Figure 39. The final session of SIP Board updating

E.3 Discussion

Overall appreciation

After the workshop, several participants explicitly expressed appreciation for the co-creation activity according to different points of view. Partners experts in co-design commented on the efficacy of analog materials (the tangible aspect of the toolkit) and in particular on the intuitiveness of the SIP Board, which allows to provide a sense of progress. Indeed, many

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participants were surprised by the amount of work produced in such a short time, and certainly the intuitive overview provided by the board facilitates a shared visualization of collective achievements.

Some Community Activators and Pilot Orchestrators started envisaging how they could use the SIP Co-design Toolkit to facilitate the creative activities in their pilot, also in combination with the community engagement methods they already employ (e.g. the Future Search Conference).

Flexibility of use of the SIP Co-Design Toolkit

In the different groups, the observed usage dynamics was varied. One group immediately decided to split into subgroups, with each subgroup working with one single ingredient category in parallel. Whereas other groups considered all the assigned categories (three or four) at the same time during the brainstorming.

For one group the initiation of the discussion required some brief warm up phase in which the challenge to address was further detailed before the creative phase of ingredient ideas generation could start. The cards were used to get inspiration at different points during the brainstorming and to further check whether something was missing.

In other cases, the cards were used more systematically, to make sure each example card was elaborated with a corresponding idea fitting the given scenario.

This variety of use exactly goes into the direction of the main principle of flexibility around which the SIP Co-design Toolkit was created.

Relationships across categories

While discussing ingredients within the context of a certain category, in some cases ideas emerged that belonged to other, related categories. This provided evidence of the fact that although the ingredients categorisation was conceived to structure and guide the process of ingredients identification, still it does not hamper cross-category thinking.

Extendability of the toolkit

The openness property of the SIP Co-design Toolkit, i.e. the possibility (and encouragement) to extend the materials with further categories and cards starting from expertise and evidence on the peculiarities of the rural domain, was fully understood by participants. Many comments and suggestions were collected on the opportunity to extend the current categorisation, for example with a category collecting examples of ingredients dealing with "Ethical aspects", and the current set of ingredient Cards (for example with material related to policies or to additional types of digital applications).

What's comes after brainstorming

Although participants contributed easily and effectively to the population of the SIP Board, they were unsure of what would be the following step. As illustrated in the scenarios reported in Annex F, the typical follow-up phase to a brainstorming aimed at generating ingredients ideas would include a **refinement session** (most probably involving the facilitator and members of the core work group) in which ideas are reordered, aggregated by similarity, filtered and consolidated into a reduced number of options, to then repeat other iterative cycles of missing ingredients identification or to analyse in detail the requirements and constraints of the ingredients in the SIP Board.

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What is the benefit of digital functionalities

Not all partners were able to immediately understand how the digital functionalities of the SIP Co-design Toolkit under development (as described in Chapter 5) relate to the usage of the analogue materials. Indeed, the digital functionalities offer support to the refinement sessions described in the previous point, with the possibility of documenting the output of each collaborative workshop, easily reorganize and refine contents, record and visualise along a timeline how the collaborative work evolved, as well as introducing gamification elements that make even more effective the valorisation of collective achievements. A dedicated training session on the use of the digital toolkit will be organized within Task 3.2 at the beginning of Y2 of project development.

Annex F – Scenarios of SIP Co-design Toolkit usage

F.1 Scenario of usage for an internal meeting

This scenario exemplifies how the toolkit can be used first **by the facilitator** to prepare a work session and **by the core group** to map stakeholders

PHASE
Problem definition

ACTIVITY
Stakeholder mapping

PARTICIPANTS INVOLVED

In this phase only **the facilitator** and **the core project group** are involved. They already defined an area of intervention and outlined some key issues to consider. They need to proceed towards a better definition of the problem.

1 STEP | MEETING PREPARATION

The facilitator prepares a co-design activity

The facilitator checks the project deadlines and goals and reflects on the opportunity to call a meeting with the core group to decide who to involve in the next phases and how

The facilitator takes out of the drawer the SIP Co-design Toolkit that she has already downloaded and printed out, following the instructions

The facilitator selects materials that will support a brainstorming to map stakeholders related to the rural challenge to be solved. She selects **INGREDIENT CARDS** and **REFLECTION QUESTIONS** from the "People" category and a **CANVAS** for stakeholder mapping.

The facilitator plans how to organize the meeting with the core group. She decides the timing of the discussion and in which phases the different materials will be used.

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2 STEP | DURING THE MEETING

The core group meets to decide who to involve in the next phases of the project

During the meeting a brainstorming session is organized. CARDS are used to encourage everyone at the table to reflect and propose potential stakeholders starting from the categories identified in the CARDS.

After the brainstorming, the "stakeholder mapping" CANVAS is used to cluster the ideas of all the participants.

Looking at the canvas, it is evident that there are only a few representatives of civil society. The REFLECTION QUESTIONS are used to spot the fact that women are underrepresented. CARDS are inspected again, and the idea of finding a "Local Hero" and to consider the local association of women is considered. They integrate the CANVAS with new ideas.

In final part of the meeting, the group reviews what emerged from the discussion and they populate the SIP BOARD. They look at the board and decide what other important ingredients should be discussed and negotiated in the next phases.

HOW THE TOOLKIT WAS USED

- **Preparatory activity:** The facilitator printed a category of CARDS and a CANVAS relevant for the discussion
- **Core Group activity:** The core group met together, they read and discussed the CARDS, they used post-its to write names of identified ingredients and put them on the CANVAS. The REFLECTION QUESTIONS allowed to identify other ingredients.
- **Board update:** They altogether took the post-its and organized them on the SIP BOARD to record progress

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F.2 Scenario of usage for a workshop with stakeholders

This scenario exemplifies how the toolkit can be used to manage a co-design **workshop with an enlarged set of stakeholders** to envision digital solutions to tackle rural areas challenges

PHASE
Solution definition

ACTIVITY
Exploration of
alternative digital
solutions

PARTICIPANTS INVOLVED

In this phase **the facilitator and the core project group** are involved, as well as an **enlarged set of stakeholders**. The challenge has already been defined. It is now time to explore some possible digital solutions.

**1 STEP |
WORKSHOP
PREPARATION**

The facilitator prepares the materials for a workshop whose goal is to start reflecting on potential digital solutions

The facilitator reflects on the fact that during the stage of solution definition, it would be appropriate to organize an event where groups of stakeholders are invited to explore alternative digital solutions.

The facilitator takes out of the drawer the SIP Co-design Toolkit that she has already downloaded and printed out, following the instructions

The facilitator selects materials that will support a brainstorming to explore possible digital solutions related to the rural challenge at hand. She selects INGREDIENT CARDS and REFLECTION QUESTIONS from the "Digital apps" category and a CANVAS for envisaging use scenarios for technology.

The facilitator carefully plans how to organize the workshop with the enlarged number of stakeholders. She decides how to split participants in groups, the timing of the discussion and in which phases the different materials will be used.

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2 STEP | WORKSHOP EXECUTION

Participants split into small groups to use the material (cards and canvases)

The workshop activity is organized in small groups of 4-6 people. The task given to participants is to try and reflect on the value of digitalization in rural areas.

They use the Digital Enablers CANVAS to manage the discussion. Each group is asked to review the CARDS describing examples of digital enablers and to answer some questions in relation to their territory.

The facilitator summarizes all the insights collected during the workshop.

At the end of the group work, the different groups present their scenarios and discuss the opportunities for digital innovation.

The facilitator adds on the SIP BOARD some ideas of digital ingredients that have emerged from the discussion.

However, a decision has not yet been taken regarding the final digital solution to be implemented. The facilitator decides to organize a new meeting with the core working group to determine how to proceed.

HOW THE TOOLKIT WAS USED

- **Preparatory activity:** The facilitator selected a category of CARDS and a CANVAS relevant for the discussion
- **Public workshop:** The enlarged group of stakeholders read and discussed the CARDS and related REFLECTION QUESTIONS. This provided stimulus for the activity with a SEROI+ CANVAS
- **Elaboration activity:** The facilitator reflected on the collected data, extracted a set of ingredients that should not be forgotten
- **Board update:** The facilitator adds the identified ingredients to the SIP BOARD to record progress

Annex G – Exploration of alternative designs for the SIP Board

G.1 Base layout

Figure 40 shows the base graphical layout for the SIP Board that was ultimately selected for the rendering of the first version of the SIP Co-design Toolkit in its printable form.

Figure 40. Base layout for the SIP Board

G.2 Layout based on the Double Diamond approach

Figure 41 shows an alternative graphical layout for the SIP Board that is inspired to the Double Diamond design methodology²⁰, which advocates for the distinction between the two phases of problem exploration and solution exploration. In this alternative layout the different

²⁰ <https://www.designcouncil.org.uk/our-resources/the-double-diamond/>.

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SIP ingredient categories are grouped closer to the design phase in which they are most useful.

Figure 41. Layout for the SIP Board inspired to the Double Diamond design methodology

G.3 Layout suggesting a three-phase SIP co-creation process

The graphical layout in Figure 42 is an elaboration of the one in Figure 41 that explicitly adds visibility to the important phase of stakeholders and community engagement, which is essential in participatory design approaches.

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Figure 42. Layout for the SIP Board based on an extension of the Double Diamond approach